

Agents of Inclusion: Experiences of Gender and Development Advocates in Mainstreaming Gender Responsive Practices in the Academe

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ABSTRACT: This phenomenological study explored the lived experiences of nine (9) Gender and Development (GAD) advocates in selected higher education institutions in the Island Garden City of Samal (IGACOS). Specifically, it aimed to examine the experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms, of GAD advocates in mainstreaming Gender and Development within higher education institutions (HEIs). Furthermore, the study proposed program implementation strategies to support and strengthen the role of GAD advocates in promoting gender-responsive policies and practices within educational institutions. A qualitative phenomenological research design was employed to capture and describe the participants' lived experiences. Data were gathered through in-depth interviews and analyzed using thematic analysis to identify recurring patterns and themes related to GAD mainstreaming. The findings revealed that the lived experiences of GAD advocates revolved around institutionalizing GAD policies and practices, implementing GAD programs and strategies, collaborating and engaging with stakeholders, and experiencing challenges in GAD implementation. In addressing these challenges, GAD advocates utilized coping mechanisms such as adapting through learning and flexibility, collaborating and building support systems, managing personal coping and emotional regulation, planning and organizing GAD implementation, and promoting advocacy through training and awareness. The study also led to the development of the "Enhancing Gender Equality Mainstreaming through Capacity Building and Institutional Support (EGEM-CBIS) Program Implementation Plan," which aims to strengthen the competencies of GAD advocates, enhance institutional support systems, improve stakeholder collaboration, and promote sustainable gender-responsive practices. The findings suggest that school administrators should strengthen institutional support for GAD by allocating sufficient resources, establishing clear policies, and ensuring consistent monitoring and evaluation mechanisms.

KEYWORDS: academe, gender responsive, mainstreaming, practices

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

The Problem and Its Setting

Gender and Development (GAD) within higher education institutions (HEIs) serves as a strategic framework for promoting gender equality and inclusivity in academic settings. In the Philippines, the Gender and Development Act of 1997 (Republic Act No. 9710) mandates all government agencies, including HEIs, to allocate at least 5% of their annual budget to GAD-related programs. In the Island Garden City of Samal, schools faced challenges in implementing gender-responsive practices, particularly in integrating gender-sensitive teaching strategies, addressing gender biases in classroom interactions, and ensuring equal participation of all students in academic and extracurricular activities. These gaps pointed to the need for targeted training for educators, awareness campaigns, and the development of policies that promoted gender equity in the school environment. However, these were purely observations and need to be validated specifically in the higher educational institutions (HEIs).

Even with comprehensive legal frameworks in place, higher education institutions (HEIs) still face ongoing difficulties in putting Gender and Development (GAD) programs into practice. Findings indicate that obstacles such as inadequate training, limited funding, and weak institutional support remain prevalent, making it challenging for HEIs to fully realize gender equality within academia (Palma, 2025).

On an international scale, particularly in Asia, the implementation of GAD in HEIs faces similar challenges. Research highlights that while countries like India and Japan have established policies to promote gender equality in education, the actualization of these policies is often impeded by entrenched cultural norms, limited resources, and institutional resistance. For instance, in India, the University Grants Commission has mandated the establishment of gender sensitization committees in HEIs; however, the effectiveness of these committees is often compromised by a lack of training and support (Sardar & Paria, 2024). Similarly, in Japan,

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efforts to increase women's participation in STEM fields and leadership roles are hindered by deeply rooted societal expectations and institutional barriers (Zhang & Zhu, 2024).

In the Philippine context, the implementation of GAD in HEIs also encounters significant obstacles. A study conducted at a public higher education institution revealed limited awareness of GAD concepts and laws among employees and students, with moderate levels of implementation and slight satisfaction reported. The study suggests that enhanced GAD implementation is needed to meet the growing demands for gender equality, and recommends a "Gender and Development Capability Enhancement Framework" to strengthen GAD efforts in public institutions (Palma, 2025).

In Mindanao, challenges in carrying out Gender and Development (GAD) initiatives continue to persist. A study conducted in secondary schools under the Ministry of Basic, Higher and Technical Education revealed that schools have shown noticeable progress in integrating GAD principles. Despite these improvements, achieving fully gender-responsive education remains difficult due to limited resources and persistent cultural barriers (Talib-Bauda et al., 2025).

However, despite existing studies on Gender and Development (GAD) in higher education institutions, several gaps remain evident. Contextually, most research focuses on national or general institutional settings, with limited attention to specific local contexts such as the Island Garden City of Samal (IGACOS), resulting in a lack of understanding of how socio-cultural and institutional factors influence GAD mainstreaming in this area. Methodologically, prior studies have largely relied on quantitative or policy-based approaches, with minimal use of qualitative methods that capture the lived experiences of GAD advocates, thereby limiting deeper insights into their actual practices and challenges. Substantively, while general barriers to GAD implementation are documented, there is insufficient exploration of the specific roles, experiences, and coping strategies of GAD advocates in HEIs, as well as how these can inform more effective program implementation for advancing gender equality.

The study would hold social relevance by contributing to the advancement of inclusive and equitable academic environments. Through an examination of the challenges and strategies of Gender and Development (GAD) advocates, it would enhance scholarly understanding of gender dynamics in higher education, thereby enriching the existing body of knowledge with empirical evidence. The findings would inform gender-responsive policies, programs, and institutional practices, while their dissemination through academic journals, conferences, and workshops would ensure that key stakeholders, including educators and policymakers, could utilize the insights to support evidence-based initiatives that promote gender equality in education.

Research Question

This study applied the phenomenological approach to explore the following central research questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of GAD Advocates in mainstreaming gender and development within higher education institutions?
2. How do GAD Advocates cope with the challenges of mainstreaming gender and development within higher education institutions?
3. What program implementation can be proposed based on the findings?

Objectives of the Study

The study looked into the lived experiences of GAD Advocates in mainstreaming gender-responsive practices in the academe. Specifically, it was seeking to:

1. determine the lived experiences of GAD Advocates in mainstreaming gender and development within higher education institutions.
2. understand how GAD Advocates cope with the challenges of mainstreaming gender and development within higher education institutions, and
3. develop a program implementation based on the findings to support GAD advocates.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to explore how Gender and Development (GAD) advocates mainstreamed gender and development within higher education institutions. It specifically sought to understand the processes, strategies, and practices they employed in integrating gender-responsive initiatives into institutional policies, programs, and academic activities. In addition, the study aimed to examine the lived experiences of GAD advocates in order to provide a deeper understanding of how gender mainstreaming was operationalized within the academic context.

Furthermore, this study sought to identify how GAD advocates coped with the challenges they encountered in mainstreaming gender and development within higher education institutions. It also aimed to develop a proposed program implementation based on the findings of the study to strengthen and enhance GAD initiatives. The proposed program was intended to address identified gaps, improve institutional support, and promote more effective and sustainable gender mainstreaming practices in higher education institutions.

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Significance of the study

Gender mainstreaming in higher education institutions has become a crucial mandate to ensure inclusivity, equity, and the dismantling of systemic barriers that hinder both students and employees from fully participating in academic life. Central to this effort are the Gender and Development (GAD) Advocates who serve as agents of inclusion, tasked with translating policies into concrete programs and initiatives that promote gender sensitivity and equality. Despite their critical role, the lived experiences, challenges, and perceptions of these focal persons remained underexplored, leaving a gap in understanding how they navigated institutional structures, advocated for gender-responsive practices, and sustained inclusive academic environments. Conducting this study was therefore necessary to illuminate their voices, capture their realities, and generate insights that could strengthen gender mainstreaming efforts, inform policy directions, and contribute to a more equitable higher education landscape. The study was viewed to be significant because of the following reasons:

To GAD Advocates. The study would be highly relevant to GAD Advocates as it validated their roles and contributions in advancing gender equality within higher education institutions. By documenting their lived experiences, the study provided a platform for their voices, challenges, and achievements to be recognized, offering both affirmation and critical reflection on their work. The findings could serve as a resource for strengthening their capacity, guiding them in refining strategies that promote inclusivity, and addressing barriers that hindered effective policy implementation. It also fostered a sense of professional identity and empowerment, reinforcing their position as vital agents of change who influence institutional policies, shape academic culture, and ensure that the principles of fairness and equality are upheld across all levels of education.

To Learners. The study would be important to students because it emphasized the creation of a safe, equitable, and supportive learning environment where everyone could thrive regardless of gender. Understanding the experiences of GAD Focal Persons allowed students to see how gender-responsive policies and programs were designed, implemented, and sustained within higher education institutions. These efforts would promote inclusivity, protect students from discrimination, harassment, and bias, and foster respect and equal opportunities in academics and campus life. The findings of this study could also empower students to appreciate the role of gender mainstreaming in shaping fairer educational spaces and inspire them to become advocates of equality and inclusivity in their own spheres.

To Teachers. The study would be highly relevant to teachers as it provided valuable insights into how gender and development initiatives could enhance inclusive practices in teaching and learning. By exploring the experiences of GAD Focal Persons, teachers could better understand the strategies and policies that supported gender equality, helping them create classrooms that respect diversity and promote equal participation among students. This knowledge strengthened their capacity to integrate gender-sensitive approaches in lesson planning, classroom management, and student engagement. The study also highlighted how teachers played a crucial role in reinforcing inclusivity, ensuring that education not only imparts knowledge but also cultivates fairness, respect, and empowerment among learners.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

This study explored the lived experiences of Gender and Development (GAD) advocates in mainstreaming gender and development within selected higher education institutions. It focused on how GAD advocates integrate gender-responsive initiatives into institutional policies, programs, academic activities, and organizational practices, particularly in teaching, research, extension, and administrative functions. The study also examined the strategies and processes they employ in implementing gender mainstreaming, as well as the challenges they encounter and the coping mechanisms they use in addressing these challenges. Anchored on a phenomenological research design, the study aimed to capture the meaning and essence of their lived experiences in promoting gender and development within the academic environment. The findings of the study also served as the basis for proposing a program implementation intended to strengthen and enhance GAD initiatives in higher education institutions.

However, the study was limited to selected GAD advocates in higher education institutions and did not include other stakeholders such as students, faculty members not directly involved in GAD programs, or institutional administrators, who may have provided additional perspectives on gender mainstreaming. As a qualitative phenomenological inquiry, the findings were based on the participants' subjective experiences and therefore may not be generalizable to all higher education institutions. The study focused on describing processes, strategies, challenges, and coping mechanisms rather than measuring the effectiveness of GAD programs using quantitative indicators. In addition, the depth of the findings depended on the openness and willingness of participants to share their experiences during data collection, and the limited number of participants and time constraints may have influenced the breadth of perspectives gathered.

Definition of Terms

For the purpose of this study, the following terms were operationally defined to ensure precision and clarity in the use of concepts. These definitions were provided to guide readers in understanding the scope, delimitations, and central focus of the research.

Agents of Inclusion refer to GAD Advocates who actively promote gender equality and inclusivity within higher education institutions through the implementation and advocacy of gender-responsive policies and programs. The term highlights their role in

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influencing institutional practices, fostering equitable participation, and shaping an academic environment grounded in fairness and respect.

Experiences of GAD Advocates pertain to the lived narratives, reflections, and insights of GAD Advocates as they engage in mainstreaming gender in higher education institutions. The term captures both the challenges they confront and the opportunities in promoting gender-responsive practices.

GAD Advocates refer to designated individuals in higher education institutions tasked with leading, implementing, and monitoring gender and development programs and policies. They serve as advocates of inclusion, ensuring that institutional practices, policies, and initiatives align with the principles of gender equality and inclusivity in academia.

Mainstreaming Gender Responsive Practices refers to the systematic integration of gender perspectives into policies, programs, and institutional practices within higher education. It involves the deliberate effort of GAD Focal Persons to promote equality, inclusivity, and sensitivity across academic structures, decision-making processes, and campus culture.

Academe refers to higher education institutions that serve as centers for teaching, learning, and research where gender and development initiatives are implemented. It specifically denotes the academic environment in which GAD focal persons carry out their roles in fostering gender inclusivity and equality.

RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

This section discussed the experiences of GAD Focal Persons in mainstreaming gender and development within higher education institutions. Specifically, it presented their challenges and coping mechanisms of the GAD advocates. These experiences prompted the researcher to come up with a proposed program implementation relevant to strengthening GAD practices. The compiled literature and related studies were used to support the findings of this research and provided a deeper understanding of how GAD Focal Persons navigated the complexities of advancing gender-responsive initiatives in academic settings. Specifically, these were used in the discussion part of the study.

Related Literature

Lived Experiences of GAD Advocates in Mainstreaming Gender and Development within HEI. Gender and Development is a framework that advances gender equality, inclusiveness, and human rights in development efforts (Nanni, 2023). It recognizes women as active participants in development rather than merely beneficiaries. On a global scale, initiatives such as the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women and the Beijing Platform for Action have encouraged many countries to establish gender-responsive policies and legislation (Freeman, 2019; Palma, 2025). Nevertheless, gender inequality continues to exist in various institutions, including higher education institutions, where issues involving discrimination and unequal opportunities remain apparent (Rosa & Clavero, 2022; Johnson, 2023; Ali et al., 2023).

In the Philippines, GAD mainstreaming in higher education institutions (HEIs) is guided by national policies such as the Republic Act No. 9710 and CHED Memorandum

Order No. 01, Series of 2015. These policies mandate the integration of gender perspectives into instruction, research, extension, and administration, as well as the allocation of at least 5% of institutional budgets for GAD programs (Manuel, 2024). The Philippine Commission on Women (PCW) further supports these efforts through the Gender and Development Strategic Plan, which provides a national framework for gender mainstreaming.

The institutionalization of GAD policies involves embedding gender perspectives into organizational structures, processes, and culture. Effective GAD implementation requires comprehensive policy frameworks, institutional commitment, capacity building, and continuous monitoring and evaluation. However, barriers such as resistance to change, limited awareness, and cultural norms continue to challenge the integration of gender-responsive practices in HEIs (Tindowen et al., 2025; Rodriguez, 2019).

Coping Mechanism of GAD Advocates on the Challenges in Mainstreaming Gender and Development within HEI. Despite the challenges in implementing Gender and Development (GAD) initiatives, several opportunities support the effective mainstreaming of GAD policies in higher education institutions (HEIs). In general, the establishment of comprehensive policy frameworks, strong institutional commitment, and continuous capacity-building initiatives are recognized as key enablers of successful GAD implementation (Perez et al., 2025). These elements provide a foundation for integrating gender perspectives into institutional structures and processes. Moreover, leadership support plays a crucial role in advancing GAD programs, as it ensures the allocation of resources, prioritization of gender initiatives, and promotion of inclusive policies within institutions (Hernandez et al., 2022; Tindowen et al., 2025).

In addition, the development of GAD offices and the implementation of the Gender and Development Focal Point System (GFPS) contribute to more organized and systematic program implementation. These structures clarify roles and responsibilities, strengthen accountability, and enhance sustainability of gender-related initiatives (Gil, 2021; Mihrete, 2021). Furthermore, capacity building and professional development opportunities enable faculty and staff to effectively integrate gender perspectives into teaching,

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research, and administrative functions, thereby promoting a gender-responsive institutional culture (Palma, 2025; Hernandez et al., 2022).

Similarly, collaboration and networking with government agencies, nongovernment organizations, and other HEIs provide access to resources, technical expertise, and best practices in gender mainstreaming (Tindowen et al., 2025; Mihrete, 2021). The integration of GAD concepts into academic curricula also serves as a vital strategy in promoting awareness and fostering critical thinking among students regarding gender issues (Gil, 2021; Palma, 2025). Additionally, the use of digital platforms enhances the delivery and monitoring of GAD programs, allowing wider participation and improved documentation (Hernandez et al., 2022).

Likewise, research and data collection strengthen evidence-based planning and policy formulation, while community engagement and extension programs expand the impact of GAD initiatives beyond the campus (Mihrete, 2021; Gil, 2021). Aligning institutional programs with national and international frameworks further enhances legitimacy, access to resources, and institutional commitment to gender equality (Palma, 2025). Finally, recognition and incentive mechanisms encourage active participation and sustain engagement in GAD activities, fostering a culture of inclusivity within HEIs (Hernandez et al., 2022; Gil, 2021).

Related Studies

Several empirical studies have examined the implementation of GAD in higher education institutions. Hernandez et al. (2022) found that while HEIs demonstrate commitment to GAD integration, challenges such as unclear policy frameworks and insufficient capacity building hinder full institutionalization. Similarly, Tindowen et al. (2025) identified both enabling factors, such as institutional support and policy frameworks, and barriers, including limited awareness, resistance to change, and inadequate resources.

Studies in the Philippine context highlight the practical implementation of GAD programs. Manuel (2024) documented initiatives such as gender-responsive curricula, training programs, and awareness campaigns in institutions like Central Philippine University, West Visayas State University, and the University of the Philippines Los Baños. However, Gil (2021) reported persistent issues in HEIs, including lack of support, inadequate training, and weak compliance with GAD mandates. Galamgam et al. (2021) further noted gaps in policy implementation even in basic education institutions.

Research also emphasizes the role and challenges of GAD advocates. Gil (2025) identified lack of training, limited resources, and resistance to change as major barriers faced by GAD focal persons in HEIs. Similarly, Mihrete (2021) found that weak leadership support, absence of dedicated personnel, and insufficient training hinder effective GAD implementation in universities. In Mindanao, Palma (2025) reported limited awareness of GAD concepts, moderate implementation, and low satisfaction among stakeholders, indicating the need for stronger GAD initiatives.

Additional studies highlight key issues affecting GAD implementation, including limited awareness and understanding of gender concepts (Palma, 2025; Tindowen et al., 2025), insufficient training and capacity building (Gil, 2021; Mihrete, 2021), inadequate institutional support and resources (Hernandez et al., 2022; Palma, 2025), resistance to organizational change (Tindowen et al., 2025), weak monitoring systems (Hernandez et al., 2022), cultural barriers (Mihrete, 2021), poor coordination (Gil, 2021), low stakeholder participation (Palma, 2025), inconsistent policy implementation (Mihrete, 2021), limited leadership support (Hernandez et al., 2022), and gaps between policy and practice (Palma, 2025; Tindowen et al., 2025).

On the other hand, empirical studies provide concrete evidence on how these opportunities are implemented in actual institutional settings. For instance, Xavier University established a Gender and Development Office in 2023, which plays a key role in planning, implementing, monitoring, and evaluating GAD programs under the GAD Focal Point System (Xavier University, 2025). Similarly, Far Eastern University (FEU) has developed a GAD Desk that leads in promoting gender awareness, coordinating institutional activities, and collaborating with student organizations to strengthen inclusivity on campus (Far Eastern University, 2024).

In the Philippine context, studies highlight the significant roles of GAD advocates or Gender Focal Persons (GFPs) in mainstreaming gender policies. According to the Philippine Commission on Women, GFPs are responsible for integrating gender perspectives across institutional operations, including planning, budgeting, and evaluation of GAD programs (Philippine Commission on Women, 2025). The Bangsamoro Transition Authority (2021) further outlines their responsibilities, such as supervising program implementation and ensuring compliance with GAD plans and budgets.

Furthermore, empirical research in Mindanao by Palma (2025) revealed that awareness and implementation of GAD initiatives significantly influence stakeholder satisfaction. The study found that increased awareness leads to better perceptions of GAD implementation, highlighting the importance of strengthening gender-related programs in HEIs. In addition, several studies identify the specific roles performed by GAD advocates, including policy planning, advocacy, capacity building, coordination, monitoring and evaluation, and ensuring compliance with national mandates (Gil, 2021; Hernandez et al., 2022; Tindowen et al., 2025).

Moreover, GAD advocates contribute to research and documentation, support student engagement and community outreach, and provide advisory roles in policy development (Mihrete, 2021; Palma, 2025). These functions help bridge the gap between policy formulation and actual implementation. The studies emphasize that through sustained efforts in advocacy, training, and

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collaboration, GAD advocates play a vital role in promoting an institutional culture of inclusivity and ensuring the long-term sustainability of gender mainstreaming initiatives in HEIs (Gil, 2021; Mihrete, 2021).

The gathered literature and studies highlighted that GAD advocates played a critical role in advancing gender mainstreaming in higher education institutions, serving as catalysts for institutional transformation toward inclusivity and equality. While their efforts were marked by opportunities to influence policy formulation, academic programs, and organizational culture, they also faced persistent challenges such as limited resources, resistance to change, and varying levels of institutional support. Their lived experiences reflected a balance between navigating structural and cultural barriers and leveraging opportunities for advocacy, awareness, and capacitybuilding initiatives. As agents of inclusion, GAD advocates not only ensure compliance with gender and development mandates but also foster environments that promote equity, respect, and empowerment across the academic community. These findings underscored the complexities of their roles, revealed the interplay of challenges and opportunities in mainstreaming gender, and affirmed their contributions as pivotal in shaping a more inclusive and gender-responsive higher education landscape.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study was mainly anchored on Gender Mainstreaming Theory by Council of Europe (1998 as cited in Kataeva et al., 2024). The Council of Europe defined gender mainstreaming as a strategy to incorporate a gender equality perspective into all policy processes at every level and stage, by reorganizing, improving, developing, and evaluating policies. This approach aims to consider the diverse needs and circumstances of both women and men to ensure that policies benefit everyone equally, enhancing gender equality by addressing often hidden inequalities, and complementing specific women's rights initiatives with a dual approach.

This theory provided a framework for understanding how gender perspectives can be systematically integrated into institutional policies, programs, and practices. This theory underscored the role of GAD advocates in promoting equality, ensuring that gender considerations are embedded in decision-making processes rather than treated as peripheral concerns. By applying this lens, the study explored how GAD advocates navigated institutional structures, influence policy implementation, and advocated for inclusive practices that address both overt and subtle forms of gender bias in academia. Furthermore, it highlighted the importance of transforming institutional culture, promoting equitable opportunities for all genders, and sustaining long-term change in higher education settings.

Another theory that served as a foundation for this study is the Institutional Theory developed by John W. Meyer and Brian Rowan (1977, as cited in Kauppi, 2021). This theory aims to explain the reasons behind organizational behavior and the impact of behavioral patterns within a wider interorganizational setting. It further describes how organizations adopt specific practices, norms, and structures in order to conform to societal expectations.

In the context of this study, this theory provided a framework for understanding how organizational structures, norms, and rules influence the implementation of gender mainstreaming initiatives. This theory highlighted the role of institutional pressures, both formal policies and informal cultural expectations, in shaping practices within academic settings. Applying this perspective allowed the study to examine how GAD advocates navigated institutional constraints, aligned their initiatives with organizational mandates, and promoted gender-inclusive policies while negotiating resistance or inertia within the system. Furthermore, Institutional Theory underscored the importance of legitimacy and conformity, offering insights into how gender mainstreaming efforts were formalized, sustained, and integrated into the culture of higher education institutions.

This study was also aligned with Feminist Theory by Butler (1990 as cited in Allen, 2023). This theory highlighted that gender is not an innate quality but a performative act created through repeated, socially learned behaviors and interactions. This theory challenged the traditional binary understanding of sex and gender, suggesting that the repeated performance of gender is what produces the illusion of a stable, internal gender identity, rather than expressing one. Butler's ideas have significantly impacted feminist and queer theory, promoting a more inclusive understanding of identity and encouraging the questioning of oppressive social norms.

In this study, this theory provided a critical lens to examine how gender identities, norms, and power dynamics shaped experiences within academic higher institutions in Island Garden City of Samal. This theory emphasized the socially constructed nature of gender and the importance of challenging inequities, which aligned with the role of GAD advocates in advocating for inclusive practices and policies. By applying this perspective, the study explores the lived experiences of Gender and Development (GAD) advocates as agents of inclusion, focusing on the challenges they encountered and the coping strategies they employed while identifying, confronting, and navigating structural and cultural barriers in mainstreaming gender-responsive practices in the academe. Moreover, Feminist Theory helped illuminate the strategies employed to empower marginalized groups, foster equity, and promote transformative change in institutional culture, thereby deepening the understanding of GAD advocates' contributions to mainstreaming gender.

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CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This study employed the Input–Process–Output (IPO) model as its conceptual framework to explain the lived experiences of Gender and Development (GAD) advocates in mainstreaming gender-responsive practices in the academe and how these experiences were transformed into meaningful outcomes.

The IPO model illustrates the relationship among the input, the process undertaken to analyze the input, and the resulting output of the study. In this research, the input consisted of the lived experiences of GAD advocates, including the challenges they encountered in implementing gender-responsive initiatives. The process involved the systematic collection and analysis of data through in-depth interviews, key informant interviews, and thematic analysis to identify their coping mechanisms, strategies, and insights. The output of the study was the proposed program implementation designed to promote a comprehensive and integrated approach to Gender and Development (GAD) mainstreaming within higher education institutions.

Through the IPO framework, the study provides a clear and organized structure for understanding how the experiences of GAD advocates were carefully examined and interpreted to generate evidence-based program recommendations that may strengthen and improve gender-responsive mainstreaming practices in the academe, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The Study's Conceptual Paradigm

CHAPTER 2 METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the methodological framework of the study, which explores the experiences of GAD advocates in mainstreaming gender in academia using a qualitative phenomenological approach. It discusses the research design, sources of data, research participants, and the research instrument used in gathering information, as well as the data collection procedure and data analysis process applied in interpreting the findings. It also includes the ethical considerations observed to ensure the protection and confidentiality of participants, along with the strategies used to establish the trustworthiness of the study such as credibility, dependability, confirmability, and transferability. This chapter outlines the systematic procedures followed in conducting the research.

Research Design

This study was anchored on a qualitative research approach, which emphasizes the in-depth exploration and understanding of social and educational phenomena through participants' lived experiences rather than numerical measurement. As emphasized by Naeem et al. (2023), qualitative research focuses on generating rich, contextualized descriptions that capture human perspectives and meanings. In this study, it provided a suitable framework for examining the lived experiences of GAD Advocates as they

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mainstreamed gender and development in higher education institutions, allowing them to express their challenges, strategies, and insights in their own voices.

In addition, the study employed a phenomenological research design, which centers on understanding the essence of lived experiences as perceived and interpreted by individuals. According to Frechette et al. (2020), phenomenology seeks to uncover how people make meaning of their experiences in real-life contexts. In this study, it was used to explore how GAD Advocates experienced, understood, and navigated the process of gender mainstreaming, including the challenges they encountered and the coping strategies they employed within academic institutions.

The use of both qualitative approach and phenomenological design was justified by the nature of the problem, which required a deep and contextual understanding of human experiences rather than statistical analysis. This approach allowed the researcher to capture the complexity and subjectivity of GAD Advocates' experiences in mainstreaming gender in higher education. It also enabled the identification of meaningful patterns and insights that can inform institutional practices, policies, and program development aimed at strengthening gender-responsive initiatives. It illuminates the challenges they face, such as limited institutional support, competing professional responsibilities, and resistance to gender-responsive initiatives. These challenges reflect broader concepts in gender mainstreaming, particularly the difficulties of integrating gender-responsive practices within institutional structures traditionally shaped by patriarchal norms and limited policy support (United Nations Women, 2023; UNESCO, 2022). GAD advocates often encounter resistance to change, inadequate funding, and insufficient training opportunities, which may hinder the sustainability of gender-responsive initiatives in higher education institutions (World Bank, 2023; OECD, 2021).

The study was further guided by key philosophical assumptions, namely ontology, epistemology, axiology, methodology, and rhetoric, which shaped its overall direction and conduct. Ontologically, reality was viewed as multiple and subjective, constructed from the diverse experiences of GAD Advocates. Epistemologically, knowledge was seen as co-constructed through participants' reflections and interpretations. Axiologically, the study recognized the influence of values and subjectivity in shaping understanding while maintaining ethical reflexivity. Methodologically, it followed an inductive qualitative process grounded in participants' lived realities. Lastly, rhetorically, the study utilized descriptive and narrative language to present authentic participant voices and experiences in a meaningful and contextualized manner.

Sources of Data

This study utilized qualitative data gathered through in-depth interviews to explore the lived experiences of GAD Advocates in mainstreaming gender and development within higher education institutions. Open-ended questions were used to allow participants to freely share their experiences, challenges, and strategies in implementing gender mainstreaming initiatives. This method enabled the collection of rich, detailed, and context-based narratives that provided meaningful insights into how participants understood and navigated their roles in promoting gender-responsive practices in their institutions.

In addition to primary data from interviews, secondary data were also reviewed to support and strengthen the findings of the study. These included relevant documents such as institutional reports, policy guidelines, journal articles, books, and other published materials related to gender and development mainstreaming in higher education. The use of these secondary sources helped provide contextual background, theoretical grounding, and comparative insights that enriched the interpretation of the interview data and ensured a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon under investigation.

Participants

This phenomenological study involved nine (9) informants in the in-depth interview. They were the GAD advocates in the selected higher educational institutions of Island Garden City of Samal (IGACOS). 1 school from Local University and Colleges (LUC), 1 school State university and colleges, and 1 private school. Each needed to fulfil the selection criteria aligned with the research objectives. This number corresponded with Subedi's (2021) recommendation that phenomenological research typically engages three to fifteen participants to generate rich, meaningful insights. Such a sample was considered sufficient to achieve data saturation, enabling the lived experiences of participants to be explored thoroughly and authentically represented within the study.

The research adopted purposive sampling as a deliberate strategy for selecting participants, given its effectiveness in qualitative inquiry. This method involves the intentional identification of individuals who possess specific qualifications or experiences relevant to the research focus, ensuring that their narratives contribute meaningful and comprehensive insights (Campbell et al., 2020). As a non-probability technique, purposive sampling provides flexibility in determining participants whose perspectives are most relevant to the objectives of the study.

Additionally, the inclusion, exclusion, and withdrawal criteria were clearly defined to ensure that the data gathered were relevant and aligned with the purpose of the study. Only GAD advocates who had been actively involved in gender mainstreaming initiatives within academic institutions for at least three years were included, as their experience was considered sufficient to provide meaningful insights into the processes and challenges of promoting gender inclusivity. Individuals who did not meet these criteria were excluded to maintain the focus of the study. Informants were also allowed to withdraw at any time, ensuring respect for their

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autonomy and adherence to ethical standards. This approach ensured that the selected informants could provide credible and experience-based accounts relevant to the study.

Research Instrument

Qualitative data can be gathered through a variety of methods, including interviews, discussions, and the examination of relevant documents or audio-visual materials. In line with these approaches, this study will employ in-depth interviews to explore the lived experiences of GAD Advocates in implementing gender mainstreaming initiatives within higher education institutions. These techniques allow informants to provide rich, contextually grounded accounts of their experiences, challenges, and strategies (Bazen et al., 2021). Informants responded to thoughtfully designed openended questions, enabling them to share detailed reflections that illuminated their perspectives and professional practices. Such narratives facilitated the identification of recurring patterns, concepts, and themes, contributing to a deeper understanding of the phenomenon under investigation. A copy of the research instrument is attached in Appendix A.

In-depth interviews serve as a primary tool in qualitative research, offering a direct means to capture participants' experiences, perceptions, beliefs, and professional practices relevant to the study. These interviews are guided by clear objectives to ensure that each interaction meaningfully addresses the research questions (Monday, 2020). Informants were acknowledged as experts on their own experiences, while I assumed the role of a careful listener. Through open-ended questioning, informants were encouraged to provide comprehensive, nuanced, and reflective responses, yielding valuable experiences, insights into the processes, challenges, and strategies involved in gender mainstreaming within their institutions.

Within this phenomenological inquiry, informants articulated their experiences in their own words during interviews. I adapted the sequence or phrasing of questions and posed follow-up prompts to elicit deeper clarification or richer explanations. This approach aimed to capture the essence of informants' lived experiences and supported the identification of key themes. Throughout data collection, I maintained an impartial stance, avoiding verbal or nonverbal signals that could influence participants' narratives, thus ensuring the credibility, authenticity, and trustworthiness of the data.

Data collection took place in settings that were convenient and comfortable for informants, including their workplaces whenever possible. The study drew information from nine in-depth interviews. To enhance the depth, credibility, and contextual understanding of the findings, supplementary sources such as scholarly articles, journals, and books were reviewed, providing theoretical frameworks, empirical evidence, and diverse perspectives relevant to the experiences of GAD Advocates in promoting gender inclusivity within academic institutions.

According to Santos et al. (2020), environmental triangulation in qualitative research entailed gathering data from multiple contextual settings to gain a deeper understanding of informants' subjective experiences under varying conditions. Engaging with diverse environments allowed me to examine the consistency and reliability of findings, thereby strengthening the study's credibility and applicability. This method reduced potential biases that resulted from focusing on a single context and promoted a more holistic view of the phenomenon being studied. In educational research, environmental triangulation was particularly valuable, as it acknowledged that differences in institutional, cultural, or social settings could significantly influence how informants perceived, responded to, and engaged with their surroundings.

In my study on the experiences of GAD Advocates from selected local university and colleges, state university and colleges, and private school emphasizing their experiences in mainstreaming gender and development responsive practices, I applied environmental triangulation to gather data from various contextual settings. By exploring the experiences of GAD Advocates in different schools, I compared and assessed how the mainstreaming of GAD practices was influenced by factors such as school environment, community dynamics, and available resources.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data collection process in this study followed a systematic and organized sequence of procedures. As explained by Lau and Bratby (2023), qualitative data can be obtained through various methods such as individual interviews, direct observations, and the review of audio-visual materials. These approaches allowed the researcher to gather rich and in-depth information about the participants' experiences and perspectives within their natural context.

Prior to data collection, ethical approval was secured from the Ethics Committee to ensure compliance with established research standards. This involved submitting a detailed research proposal outlining the study's purpose, methodology, and possible risks. The committee reviewed the proposal to ensure that participants' rights, confidentiality, and well-being were fully protected. After obtaining ethical clearance on December 17, 2025, and are presented in Appendix B, formal permission was requested from the Dean of the Graduate School at Rizal Memorial Colleges (RMC) on January 22, 2026, as shown in Appendix C. Authorization was subsequently granted by the Office of the President of Colleges and Universities on January 29–30, 2026, and February 13, 2026, and are attached in Appendix D. These approvals were necessary to formally conduct the study within the institution.

An interview protocol was then developed as the main data collection instrument. It consisted of open-ended questions designed to explore the experiences and practices of GAD advocates in strengthening gender-responsive initiatives. The instrument was carefully

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constructed to ensure clarity and relevance, and it underwent expert validation on November 25, 2025, December 10, 2025, and January 15, 2026 to confirm its appropriateness, as shown in Appendix E.

Before conducting the interviews, informed consent was obtained from all informants and the signed informed consent form is attached in Appendix F. I clearly explained the purpose, procedures, and significance of the study, emphasizing that participation was voluntary and that informants could withdraw at any time without consequences. Once consent was secured, one-on-one, in-depth interviews were conducted in a safe and comfortable setting to encourage open and honest responses. With permission, all interviews were audio-recorded to ensure accuracy.

After the interviews, the recordings were transcribed verbatim. The data were then analyzed using a phenomenological approach to identify recurring themes and patterns that reflected the informants' lived experiences. This process aimed to provide an accurate and meaningful interpretation of the perspectives of GAD advocates.

Throughout the study, strict measures were observed to maintain confidentiality and data security. All recordings and transcripts were stored in password-protected files, and pseudonyms were used to protect informants' identities. The data were used solely for research purposes and were securely disposed of after the completion of the study to ensure privacy and confidentiality.

Data Analysis

Humble and Mozelius (2022) described five essential phases in qualitative data analysis: data logging, anecdote collection, vignette creation, data coding, and thematic interpretation. This study focused primarily on the latter two stages, data coding and thematic analysis, since they provided a structured approach to examining the experiences of GAD Advocates in promoting gender-responsive practices within academic institutions. Data coding served as a systematic process for organizing qualitative information by breaking down extensive datasets into concise, meaningful components that directly correspond to the research objectives. Through this process, large volumes of text were divided into manageable units, allowing for the identification of recurrent ideas and emerging themes.

According to Kiger and Varpio (2022), codes that repeatedly emerged across the data often signified meaningful thematic patterns. In applying this approach, the researcher utilized visual aids such as colored highlighters or markers to identify recurring or significant ideas found in the transcribed interviews and focus group discussions. Similar coded responses were then organized into groups and given descriptive labels that reflected their core meanings.

Meanwhile, thematic analysis focuses on recognizing and interpreting the major patterns that arise from the coded data. This process allows the researcher to organize the information into coherent categories while gaining a more in-depth understanding of both the shared and distinct experiences of the participants. As explained by Saul McLeod (2024), this stage involves determining which portions of the data qualify as valid themes and interpreting them systematically to generate meaningful and comprehensive insights. In the present study, thematic analysis followed the coding stage, beginning with the organization of informants' responses from broad conceptual patterns to more refined interpretations. Data expressing similar meanings were clustered to form cohesive themes, each substantiated by at least three core ideas. To uphold confidentiality and maintain a clear structure throughout the process, informants' identifiers were encoded and consistently applied during the entire analysis phase.

The analytical framework developed by Colaizzi (1978), as referenced in Praveena and Sasikumar (2021), provided a systematic process for analyzing qualitative data, particularly focused on revealing the fundamental meanings within informants' lived experiences. This method entailed multiple stages, such as thoroughly reviewing interview transcripts, pinpointing key statements, interpreting their contextual significance, and categorizing them into coherent thematic structures. Colaizzi's approach emphasized maintaining the authenticity of informants' voices while exploring the depth and intricacy of their experiences. It was regarded as a well-established and reliable procedure in phenomenological research for generating meaningful interpretations and achieving a holistic grasp of the studied phenomenon.

For the present study, Colaizzi's method guided the analysis of interview data from GAD Advocates. Employing this approach allowed the extraction of comprehensive and insightful interpretations grounded in the advocates' narratives. By systematically following Colaizzi's sequence of analytical steps, the study ensured that the findings remained true to the participants' lived realities, providing a faithful representation of their experiences. This methodological rigor supported the overall reliability, validity, and credibility of the research outcomes.

Analyzing the Interviews. The first step in Colaizzi's method involves an in-depth review of the interview data. In this research, I began by meticulously examining the transcribed interviews to fully understand the informants' perspectives and experiences. Each transcript was read several times to ensure complete immersion in the data and to grasp the underlying meanings within their narratives. This repeated reading facilitates the identification of subtle nuances, emotions, and contextual elements expressed by each participant. Such a detailed engagement with the data provided a strong analytical foundation for the following stages, ensuring that the emerging interpretations accurately reflected the participants' authentic experiences and insights.

Identifying Key Phrases. Following the completion of the interview analysis, I identified and extracted key phrases and meaningful statements from the informants' responses. These excerpts reflected the core experiences and viewpoints of GAD advocates.

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Particular attention was given to statements that reveal the obstacles they encountered and the adaptive approaches they used to effectively mainstream GAD practices in the academe. Emphasizing these critical expressions helped surface the most insightful and relevant aspects of the data, serving as the basis for deeper thematic interpretation.

Identifying Meanings and Coding. After identifying the key phrases, I proceeded to interpret their meanings and assign specific codes to each relevant portion of the data. These codes functioned as concise markers that represented the core ideas and developing themes found within the informants' accounts. This step played a vital role in organizing and structuring the qualitative material, allowing for a more detailed and systematic examination. Through coding, recurring patterns and conceptual similarities across the interviews were recognized, forming the groundwork for deeper thematic interpretation and analysis.

Organizing Codes into Groups. After completing the coding phase, I arranged the identified codes into clusters that shared similar meanings or connections. This process facilitated the discovery of broader themes that encapsulated the diverse dimensions of the informants' experiences. By grouping related codes, the analysis became more structured and coherent, allowing the key influences and underlying factors in the transition process to emerge clearly. This approach ensured that all relevant aspects of the data were systematically integrated.

Describing the Phenomenon. At this stage, the goal was to construct a detailed portrayal of the phenomenon grounded in the GAD Advocates' lived experiences. The themes and insights identified in the previous steps were synthesized to form a coherent and comprehensive narrative. This account highlighted the challenges GAD Advocates encountered and the strategies they employed to mainstream gender and development responsive practices. Developing this thorough description allowed for a deeper understanding of their overall experiences.

Identifying the Fundamental Structure. At this phase, I identified the fundamental structure of the phenomenon by analyzing the key dimensions that characterized how GAD Advocates implemented gender and development responsive practices. The themes generated from the analysis were thoroughly examined, with emphasis placed on the most significant aspects of their lived experiences. This stage facilitated the formulation of conclusions regarding the central features of their experiences. Defining this essential structure offered a deeper understanding of the elements influencing their adaptation and underscored the critical factors that contributed to the effective integration of gender-responsive initiatives within the academic setting.

Validating the Findings. The results underwent a systematic validation process through informant and expert feedback. First, member checking was conducted by presenting the developed themes and interpretive summaries to the informants to confirm that the findings accurately reflected their lived experiences. Informants were given the opportunity to review, clarify, and validate the interpretations based on their responses. Expert validation was carried out by submitting the analyzed data, themes, and interpretations to subject-matter experts and peer reviewers. They examined the analysis in terms of accuracy, consistency, and alignment with the study's objectives and methodology. Their feedback was incorporated to refine the themes and ensure the credibility, coherence, and methodological rigor of the findings.

This validation process reinforced the credibility and dependability of the study, ensuring that the interpretations were firmly rooted in the informants' narratives. By adhering to Colaizzi's approach, the examination of interview data yielded meaningful insights and a comprehensive portrayal of the experiences of GAD Advocates in mainstreaming gender-responsive practices.

Figure 1 shows the processes of Colaizzi's thematic analysis which are applied in analyzing the data of the study. Each step which included reviewing interview transcripts, identifying significant statements, formulating meanings, clustering themes, and constructing a comprehensive description, provided a systematic and rigorous approach to analysis. Using Colaizzi's method ensured that the informants' own words were central to the interpretation, preserving the authenticity of their lived experiences while revealing underlying patterns and themes. This structured procedure captured the depth and complexity of the GAD Advocates' experiences, offering a clear and credible understanding of how they mainstreamed gender and development responsive practices.

(Colaizzi 1978, as cited in Praveena & Sasikumar, 2021)

Figure 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

Ethical Consideration

This study emphasized the utmost importance of adhering to ethical principles to ensure that the research was conducted with integrity, transparency, and respect for all participants. In the context of qualitative inquiry, ethical considerations were embedded throughout each stage of the research process, with deliberate attention given to defining the study's scope and boundaries to uphold clarity and accountability. These ethical responsibilities aligned closely with the methodological framework, particularly the commitment to protect the confidentiality, anonymity, and authenticity of participants' accounts and lived experiences. In line with this approach, the study followed the ethical guidelines set forth by the Rizal Memorial Colleges Ethics Review Committee.

Social Value. The social relevance of this study stemmed from its capacity to highlight the experiences and perspectives of GAD Advocates in implementing gender mainstreaming initiatives within academic institutions. The study offered a more comprehensive

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understanding of the difficulties they faced, the approaches they employed to address these challenges, and the significant roles they played in promoting inclusive and equitable learning environments. These findings could strengthen the professional responsibilities of GAD Advocates, foster collaboration among educators and staff, and encourage a culture of collective responsibility within educational institutions. More broadly, the results could provide useful insights for educational leaders, policymakers, and stakeholders in formulating responsive frameworks that recognize the contributions of GAD Advocates, reinforce institutional trust, and improve the quality of education by advancing equity and inclusive practices in schools.

Informed Consent Form. The researcher ensured that informed consent was secured from all participants before their involvement in the study. Each participant was provided with a thorough explanation of the study's purpose, objectives, and scope, together with a clear description of the procedures, possible risks, and anticipated benefits associated with participation. Participants were also informed of their right to refuse participation or withdraw from the study at any stage without facing any adverse consequences. A written informed consent form was provided, detailing the measures taken to maintain confidentiality, the procedures for data handling, and the assurance that participants' identities would remain anonymous. Adequate time was given for participants to read the document, raise questions, and voluntarily confirm their participation through their signature, thereby ensuring that their involvement was ethical, informed, and voluntary.

Vulnerability of Research Participants. I took deliberate measures to ensure the safety and well-being of participants throughout the study. Recognizing that GAD Advocates might feel uneasy when discussing personal experiences related to implementing gender mainstreaming initiatives, data collection was conducted in a supportive and respectful setting. Sensitive topics were approached with discretion, and participants were assured that their contributions remained confidential and anonymous. Participation was emphasized as voluntary, and individuals had the right to decline to answer specific questions or to withdraw from the study at any time without facing negative consequences. In addition, interactions were designed to minimize emotional strain or professional discomfort, and all data were securely managed to prevent unauthorized access. Through these precautions, the study maintained its ethical responsibility to protect participants from harm while preserving their dignity, trust, and sense of security throughout the research process.

Benefits, Risk, and Safety. I implemented intentional safeguards to ensure that participation in the study was both beneficial and secure, while potential risks were carefully managed. Participants were informed of the advantages of the research, which included opportunities for self-reflection, expression of professional insights, and meaningful contributions to enhancing practices that promoted gender mainstreaming within academic institutions. Alongside these benefits, participants were also made aware of possible risks, such as emotional discomfort or concerns related to professional implications, with clear strategies provided to address and mitigate these issues. Data collection was conducted in a respectful and protected environment to ensure that no interaction compromised the physical, emotional, or professional wellbeing of participants. In addition, strict measures were followed to maintain confidentiality and anonymity, including careful handling and secure storage of all data, while participants' right to withdraw from the study at any stage was consistently reinforced.

Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. I placed a strong priority on safeguarding the privacy and confidentiality of all information shared throughout the study. During data collection and analysis, personal identifiers were either removed or systematically coded to ensure that participants' identities remained protected. All research materials, including interview transcripts and audio recordings, were stored in secure, password-protected files accessible only to me. Participants were clearly informed that their contributions were handled with strict confidentiality and reported in ways that aggregated or anonymized individual perspectives. In presenting the findings, whether in written reports or academic forums, participants' narratives were portrayed carefully without revealing any identifying details. These measures preserved the integrity of participants' personal and professional information, fostered trust, and encouraged GAD Advocates to share their experiences openly and authentically.

Justice. I upheld the ethical principle of justice through the fair and respectful treatment of all participants throughout the study. The selection of GAD Advocates followed clear and non-discriminatory criteria, providing equal opportunity for eligible individuals to share their experiences, regardless of professional role, personal background, or demographic characteristics. Participation ensured that all selected individuals had equitable access to the benefits of the study, including opportunities for reflection, contributing to discussions on gender mainstreaming in academic institutions, and informing improvements in inclusive practices. At the same time, potential risks were minimized and addressed fairly across participants. Each narrative was given equal consideration during data analysis and interpretation, ensuring that no account was afforded undue emphasis or overlooked.

Transparency. I ensured transparency throughout the study by providing clear, detailed, and accurate information regarding the study's purpose, objectives, procedures, and anticipated outcomes. GAD Advocates were given a comprehensive explanation of their role in the research, the methods for data collection and analysis, and how the findings were shared. Potential risks, study limitations, and the measures established to protect participants' rights and welfare were openly communicated, allowing participants to make informed decisions about their involvement. Regular updates and clarifications were offered promoting an environment of openness and mutual trust.

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Conflict of Interest. I ensured that the study remained free from any conflict of interest through the consistent maintenance of professional boundaries and impartiality. There were no financial, personal, or institutional connections that could affect the design, conduct, analysis, or reporting of the research. Selection of participants, data collection, and interpretation of findings were guided solely by the research objectives and ethical standards, without granting undue advantage or imposing disadvantage on any individual or group. I also refrained from influencing participants' responses, allowing GAD Advocates to share their perspectives openly and authentically. These measures protected the integrity of the study, fostered trust among participants, and upheld the ethical obligation to conduct scholarly work with objectivity and fairness.

Qualification of the Researcher. I possess the necessary qualifications to conduct this study through relevant academic training, professional experience, and expertise in qualitative research methods. A background in educational management and active involvement in school leadership equips the researcher with a nuanced understanding of the challenges, responsibilities, and strategies involved in implementing gender mainstreaming initiatives within academic institutions. In addition, I received formal training in qualitative inquiry, including phenomenological research approaches, ethical practices for data collection, and systematic techniques for thematic analysis. This combination of academic preparation and practical experience enabled me to carry out the study with methodological rigor, ethical awareness, and a contextual understanding of the professional environment in which GAD Advocates operated.

Adequacy of Facilities. I ensured that adequate facilities were available to support the smooth implementation of the study through careful planning and coordination with the host institution. Appropriate spaces were prepared for individual interviews, providing a quiet, comfortable, and secure setting that encourages participants to share their experiences openly and without interruption. Necessary materials and tools, including recording devices, notebooks, and writing instruments, were provided to facilitate accurate and precise data collection. Attention was also given to the accessibility and convenience of the setting, minimizing logistical barriers that could affect participation. These preparations established a research environment that supports thorough, reliable, and ethically responsible exploration of how GAD Advocates implemented gender mainstreaming initiatives within academic institutions.

Role of the Researcher

In this qualitative phenomenological study, I served as the primary instrument of data collection, playing a central role in the design, implementation, and interpretation of the research. The study focused on the lived experiences of Gender and Development (GAD) advocates in three Higher Education Institutions in the Island Garden City of Samal, particularly in mainstreaming gender-responsive practices in the academe.

I developed semi-structured interview guides, observational protocols, and field notes to ensure that the data accurately reflected the perspectives and experiences of the GAD advocates. Informants were purposively selected based on specific inclusion criteria to ensure they had relevant experience, knowledge, and involvement in gender and development initiatives within their institutions. Through open-ended discussions, informants were able to share their lived experiences, challenges encountered, and coping strategies in promoting gender-responsive practices.

To gather rich and authentic data, I established trust, rapport, and a supportive environment with the informants. I conducted all interactions with empathy, cultural sensitivity, and respect, considering the institutional context and the professional backgrounds of the informants. This approach encouraged honest and in-depth sharing of experiences.

Ethical considerations were strictly observed throughout the study. Informed consent was obtained from all informants, and confidentiality was ensured through the use of pseudonyms and secure handling of all data. I maintained objectivity during data collection and practiced reflexivity to minimize bias and ensure fair interpretation of the findings.

I also handled the systematic transcription, coding, and thematic analysis of the data. This process allowed me to identify key themes that captured the essence of the informants' lived experiences in implementing gender-responsive practices. Field notes and observations were integrated to support a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon.

Finally, I connected the findings to relevant educational theories and gender and development frameworks. The study highlights the experiences, challenges, and strategies of GAD advocates, offering insights that may inform institutional practices, policies, and programs aimed at strengthening gender mainstreaming in higher education. Ultimately, this research served as a platform for amplifying the voices of GAD advocates in promoting inclusive and gender-responsive academic environments.

Trustworthiness of the Study

Ahmed (2024) emphasized that the strength of a study was demonstrated through the degree to which its findings were perceived as reliable and convincing by its audience. In this research, I ensured trustworthiness by attending to essential criteria, including credibility, dependability, transferability, and confirmability, which collectively maintain the rigor, validity, and integrity of the investigation.

Credibility. In qualitative research, credibility corresponds to the concept of internal validity in quantitative studies and emphasizes the trustworthiness and accuracy of the findings. It examines whether the results genuinely reflect the experiences and perspectives of informants. To enhance credibility, strategies such as prolonged engagement, triangulation, and member validation are employed

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(Rashid, 2025). In this study, I captured the authentic perspectives of GAD Advocates who have at least three years of professional experience in implementing gender mainstreaming initiatives within higher academic institutions. Prolonged engagement supported the establishment of rapport and to develop a deeper, more nuanced understanding of informants' experiences. Triangulation drew upon multiple sources of data, including in-depth interviews, and relevant institutional documents, to strengthen the validity of the findings. Member validation provided participants with the opportunity to review and confirm the accuracy of the interpretations. These strategies ensured that the study faithfully represented the lived experiences of GAD advocates and the ways in which they navigated challenges, implemented strategies, and contributed to promoting gender inclusivity within their institutions.

Transferability refers to the extent to which research findings can be applied or considered relevant in different contexts, enabling readers to determine whether the results hold meaning within their own educational or institutional settings (Stalmeijer et al., 2024). Achieving transferability required providing rich and detailed descriptions of informants, the research environment, and the procedures followed. In this study, thorough documentation of the methodology was provided to ensure clarity and transparency. Detailed accounts included the research setting, profiles of GAD Advocates with at least three years of professional experience in implementing gender mainstreaming initiatives, and the specific procedures used for data collection. All transcripts and analytical materials were included in the appendices to serve as references for future research and to enhance the credibility of the findings. In addition, all collected data were systematically organized and securely maintained in both digital and printed formats.

Confirmability refers to the degree to which research findings and interpretations are rooted in informants' experiences and data rather than influenced by the researcher's personal beliefs, assumptions, or viewpoints (Lee, 2025). Achieving confirmability requires maintaining a comprehensive audit trail that records each stage of the research process, from data collection to analysis and reporting. In this study, an audit trail was carefully maintained through the systematic organization of raw data, including transcripts from in-depth interviews with GAD Advocates who have at least three years of professional experience in implementing gender mainstreaming initiatives, as well as field notes, institutional documents, and other relevant records gathered throughout the study. All materials were securely stored to ensure transparency and allow for external verification if necessary. This detailed documentation enabled me to track analytical decisions, enhanced the credibility of the findings, and supported accurate coding and the development of meaningful themes that authentically represented informants' experiences in promoting gender inclusivity within academic institutions.

Dependability refers to the consistency and stability of research findings over time, ensuring that the results can be considered reliable and applicable for future reference (Andersson et al., 2024). It highlighted the importance of producing findings that were trustworthy, coherent, and verifiable. In this study, dependability was strengthened through triangulation, which incorporated multiple sources of data, including in-depth interviews with GAD Advocates. Additionally, peer review was conducted through consultations with research advisers and expert panelists to confirm that interpretations and conclusions remained accurate.

CHAPTER 3

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section presents the key findings of the study in relation to its three central research questions. First, it examines how GAD advocates mainstream gender and development within higher education institutions, highlighting the strategies, practices, and initiatives they employ to integrate gender responsiveness into academic and institutional processes. Second, it explores how GAD advocates cope with the challenges encountered in mainstreaming gender and development, emphasizing the mechanisms, support systems, and adaptive approaches that enable them to sustain their efforts despite existing constraints. Lastly, it presents a proposed program implementation based on the findings of the study, which aims to strengthen gender-responsive practices in the academe. The proposed program highlights strategies for enhancing institutional support, improving policy implementation, and strengthening professional development initiatives for GAD advocates within higher education institutions.

To ensure the credibility and depth of the findings, triangulation was employed in the analysis and interpretation of data. This was achieved through the comparison of narratives from nine (9) GAD advocates representing diverse institutional contexts, including local universities and colleges (LUCs), state universities and colleges (SUCs), and private higher education institutions. This variation in participants' institutional affiliations allowed for environmental triangulation, enabling the researcher to identify similarities and differences in experiences, practices, and challenges in mainstreaming gender and development across different academic settings. In addition, the findings were interpreted alongside relevant literature and existing studies on gender mainstreaming, ensuring that participants' accounts were supported and contextualized within established theoretical and empirical frameworks.

The study involved nine (9) Gender and Development (GAD) advocates from various higher education institutions, representing a diverse range of professional roles and years of experience. In terms of institutional affiliation, three (3) participants are from local universities and colleges (LUCs), namely GAD 1, a clinic head with five (5) years of experience; GAD 6, a dean of college and librarian with six (6) years of experience; and GAD 9, a GAD focal person with five (5) years of experience.

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Similarly, three (3) participants are from state universities and colleges (SUCs), including GAD 3, an instructor with four (4) years of experience; GAD 5, an Administrative Officer V with three (3) years of experience; and GAD 7, a GAD focal person with twenty (20) years of experience.

Meanwhile, three (3) participants are from private schools, namely GAD 2, a human resource officer with four (4) years of experience, GAD 8, an admission officer with three (3) years of experience, and GAD 4, who serves as both a guidance counselor and GAD focal person with three (3) years of experience.

Lived Experiences of GAD Advocates in Mainstreaming Gender and Development within HEI

The findings of this study revealed that GAD advocates in higher education institutions experience both opportunities and challenges in mainstreaming gender and development. These experiences reflect the complex process of institutionalizing gender mainstreaming, which involves translating gender-responsive policies into concrete programs, practices, and institutional commitments within the academe (UN Women, 2023; UNESCO, 2022).

Triangulation of data from interviews, cross-institutional comparisons (LUCs, SUCs, and private HEIs), and relevant literature revealed consistent patterns in the lived experiences of GAD advocates. This methodological triangulation strengthened the credibility of the findings by confirming that similar challenges and strategies exist across different institutional contexts. It also allowed for a more nuanced

interpretation of how gender mainstreaming is operationalized in varying academic environments.

GAD advocates actively work to embed gender-responsive policies within institutional frameworks and translate them into programs such as trainings, awareness campaigns, and gender-sensitive curricular initiatives. This aligns with the broader concept of gender mainstreaming as an institutional transformation strategy aimed at integrating gender equality into all levels of decision-making and implementation (World Bank, 2023).

However, despite these efforts, the findings also highlight persistent challenges, including limited institutional support, insufficient resources, varying stakeholder commitment, resistance to change, and competing organizational priorities. These barriers are consistent with global studies indicating that gender mainstreaming in higher education is often constrained by structural limitations, inadequate funding, and uneven policy enforcement (OECD, 2021; UN Women, 2023).

Despite these obstacles, GAD advocates employ adaptive strategies such as collaboration, continuous advocacy, and stakeholder engagement to sustain implementation efforts. The convergence of findings across different institutions through triangulation further confirms that while progress in gender mainstreaming is evident, sustained institutional commitment and resource allocation remain essential to fully achieve gender-responsive transformation in higher education institutions.

Table 1 presents the experiences of GAD advocates in mainstreaming Gender and Development within HEIs, highlighting the themes, sub-themes, and significant statements that emerged from the analysis.

Table 1. Lived Experiences of GAD Advocates in Mainstreaming Gender and Development within HEI

Main Theme	Sub-theme	Significant Statements
Institutionalizing GAD Policies and Practices	Policy Integration and Compliance	<p>IDI-GAD1: “About fud sa policies and practices ma’am is through gina issue na mga memorandum orders.” [Regarding the policies and practices, ma’am, these are implemented through the issuance of memorandum orders.]</p> <p>IDI- GAD2: “naga gamit ko ug sex-disggregated data sa mga documents gina integrate fud nako sa amoang mga manuals.” [Aside from using sex-disaggregated data in my documents, I also integrate these policies into our manuals.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD6: “I have policies, and these are written in our student handbook.” [I also have policies that are written in our student handbook.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD7: “its also a mandate man gud because of CMO no. 1 of the CHED. I also have mga internal policies will anchored also sa CHED and Philippine Commission on Women (PCW) .” [It is also mandated under CHED Memorandum Order (CMO) No. 1. I also have internal policies that are aligned with CHED and the Philippine Commission on Women (PCW).]</p>

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Main Theme	Sub-theme	Significant Statements
		<p>IDI-GAD8: “Naa fud ko specific na policy sa student handbook for no discrimination in admitting the students.” [I also have a specific policy in the student handbook regarding non-discrimination in student admission.]</p>
<p>Institutionalizing GAD Policies and Practices</p>	<p>Gender Responsive Systems and Processes</p>	<p>IDI-GAD1: “Our target population sa program is open to all gender apil nafud dihaa ang mga LGBTQ member nga students.” [The target population of our programs is open to all genders, including LGBTQ members and students.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD2: “Sa administrative side sex-disaggregated data used sa mga documents.” [On the administrative side, sex-disaggregated data are used in our documents.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD3: “my teaching methods and materials are inclusive ug dili gender bias.” [My teaching methods and materials are inclusive and free from gender bias.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD4: “pag magtawag sila ug student amoang gina ingon sa ilaha na pinaka safe is “they or them” kana nga pronouns aron dili gyud sila malain.” [When addressing students, we encourage them to use the safest pronouns, such as “they” or “them,” to avoid offending anyone.]</p> <p>IDI GAD6: “I recognize students of different sexes and gender preferences.” [I recognize students of different sexes and gender preferences.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD8: “Dapat Gender Fair Language nay gamiton.” [gender-fair language should be used.]</p>
<p>Implementing GAD Programs and Strategies</p>	<p>Promotion of Inclusivity and Gender Sensitivity</p>	<p>IDI-GAD1: “Every December nay World Aids Day Celebration.” [Every December, we celebrate World AIDS Day.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD2: “During sa pag conduct ug gender-sensitivity training.” [During the conduct of gender-sensitivity training.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD3: “always gina consider and gender equality.” [Gender equality is always considered.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD4: “Number one gyud kay ang empathy...” [The most important thing is empathy.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD5: “Naa me mga advertisement like sa TV, naay mga educational video.” [There are advertisements shown on television as well as educational videos.]</p>
<p>Implementing GAD Programs and Strategies</p>	<p>Training, Seminars, and Awareness Programs</p>	<p>IDI-GAD1: “naa man mi annual activities like symposiums, trainings, and orientation nga gina align fud sa DOH programs.” [We have annual activities such as symposiums, trainings, and orientations that are aligned with the programs of the Department of Health (DOH).]</p> <p>IDI-GAD2: “Sa among mga personnel personnel fud dapat maka undergo sila ug Gender Sensitivity Training aron naay silay background knowledge kung unsa ang GAD”. [Our personnel are also required to undergo Gender Sensitivity Training so that they will have background knowledge about GAD.]</p>

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Main Theme	Sub-theme	Significant Statements
		<p>IDI-GAD3: “naga tabang ko conduct sa mga GAD activities like Women’s month” [As a support system for the GAD Office, I help in conducting GAD-related activities such as Women’s Month celebrations.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD4: “I conducted seminars aside from that not just with students but also our faculties and staff ..” [In our institution, I conducted seminars not only for students but also for faculty members and staff.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD5: “I have a lot of gender activities, aside from that syempre awareness sa mga students through kanang posters. Tapos naa fud mga symposiums.” [I have many gender-related activities. Aside from that, I also raise awareness among students through posters and symposiums.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD6: “Katung mga seminars on Sexual Harassment, katung safe spaces act and others.” [such as seminars on Sexual Harassment, the Safe Spaces Act, and other related topics.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD8: Naga conduct ko ug women’s month and other GAD-related activities which is mandated fud sa CHED.” [I celebrate Women’s Month and conduct other GAD-related activities, which are mandated by CHED.]</p>
Implementing GAD Programs and Strategies	Curriculum and Academic Integration	<p>IDI-GAD3: “naka teach man gyud kog gender and society nga subject. “ [I teach the subject Gender and Society.]</p> <p>“Integrated na sa mga subjects example sa Psy 101 the understanding the self . (GAD2) [GAD concepts are already integrated into subjects such as Psy 101 the Understanding the Self.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD7: “We also have subject on gender and society....[We also offer a subject on Gender and Society.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD9: “we have gender and society nga karon.....” [We currently offer the subject Gender and Society.]</p>
Implementing GAD Programs and Strategies	Development of Inclusive Instructional Practices	<p>IDI-GAD3: “Gina ensure gyud nako that my teaching methods and materials are inclusive ug walay gender bias. “ [I ensure that my teaching methods and materials are inclusive and free from gender bias.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD7: “Since part si GAD sa pag critic sa tanan, we produce instructional materials on that, that is inclusive from what we observe sa community na pwedi namo na basis.” [Since GAD is part of the evaluation and critique process in all areas, we produce instructional materials that are inclusive and based on what we observe in the community, which can serve as our basis.]</p>
Collaborating and Engaging with Stakeholders	Inter-Office and External Collaboration	<p>IDI-GAD1: “Makipag collaborate mi sa City health office....” [We collaborate with the City Health Office.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD2: “collaboration makatabang siya aron dili kaau dali ta ma stress kay dghan man committees. [Collaboration is especially helpful because it lessens stress since there are many committees involved.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD3: “ Dapat Collaboration gyud, kay aron ma ensures that GAD initiatives are not dependent on individual effort alone.” [There should</p>

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Main Theme	Sub-theme	Significant Statements
		<p>really be collaboration because it ensures that GAD initiatives are not dependent on individual effort alone.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD4: “Every Semester naga meeting mi sabay ang drug free meeting sa tanan branches.” [Every semester, we conduct meetings together with the Drug-Free Program meetings across all branches.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD9: “Then, ang collaboration fud effective gyud siya kay naa may division of work.” [Collaboration is truly effective because there is a clear division of work.]</p>
Collaborating and Engaging with Stakeholders	Participation of Faculty, Staff, and Students	<p>IDI-GAD1: “kanang gina encourage jud namo mga students mo participate.... “ [We strongly encourage students to participate.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD2: “Ug dapat ang mga students mo join jud sila kay para rman fud nis ilaha.” [Students are also encouraged to participate because these programs are intended for their benefit.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD3: “ Aside sa gina encourage namo ang mga students nga mo participate sa discussion..“ [Aside from encouraging students to participate in discussions and activities without gender bias.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD4: “Naga adtu mi or naa mi community na gi adopt, didtua mi permi naga seminar. We provide GAD development seminar sa ilaha aside sa financial literacy.” [We regularly visit our adopted community where we conduct GAD development seminars in addition to financial literacy seminars.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD8: “ Everytime naay mga activity sa school, dhaa fud mi mahatagan ug time aron ma socialize ang mga personnel. Kanang naay mga meeting fud and other activity sa school.” [Whenever there are school activities, we are also given opportunities to socialize with other personnel. This usually happens during meetings and other school-related activities.]</p>
Collaborating and Engaging with Stakeholders	Promotion of Inclusive Participation and Support	<p>IDI-GAD1: “tanan activity namo is open for all gender same anang sa blood letting activity ug HIV testing.” [All of our activities are open to all genders, such as bloodletting activities and HIV testing.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD6: “aron ma encourage sila na mo participate we need to respect lang gyud kung unsa sila.” [To encourage participation, we simply need to respect individuals for who they are.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD4: We make sure that the activity was enjoyable and we have to make sure it was safe for them.” [We make sure that the activities are enjoyable and safe for the students.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD5: “dapat fully inform sila ug dapat I follow-up fud aron muattend gyud sila to any GAD activity.” [Participants should be fully informed and consistently followed up to ensure that they attend GAD-related activities.]</p>
Experiencing Challenges in GAD Implementation	Resource and Budget Constraints	<p>IDI-GAD1: “In addition, since under man gyud mis LGU ug gina bahin-bahin lng fud ang budget ug limited lng gyud siya.” [In addition, since we are under the LGU, the budget is divided and is quite limited.]</p>

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Main Theme	Sub-theme	Significant Statements
		<p>IDI-GAD2: "...Ikaduha, kay kulang sa budget." [Another issue is the limited budget.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD3: "Mga challenges is unang-una time and workload constraints.....And tungud sa limited resources ...Usahay fud, lack of awareness." [The main challenges include time and workload constraints. Another challenge is the limited resources. Sometimes, there is also a lack of awareness.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD9: "cguro, Kung naay enough budget, collaboration, and specially support sa administration." (GAD9) [If there is sufficient budget, strong collaboration, and especially administrative support.]</p>
Experiencing Challenges in GAD Implementation	Scheduling and Time Constraints	<p>IDI-GAD5: "Kanang usahay naay dungan nga activity i conduct sa school." (GAD5) [Sometimes, there are activities that are conducted simultaneously within the school.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD9: "Aside ana, kanang usahay naay mga overlapping activities imbis naka plan out naka then need nafud e adjust ang schedule." [Another issue is overlapping activities—sometimes even if everything is already planned, schedules still need to be adjusted.]</p>
Experiencing Challenges in GAD Implementation	Awareness and Resistance Issues	<p>IDI-GAD3: "Ang uban aside sa lack of awareness, ma mislook ang announcement or information, naa fud uban dili ganahan mo attend gyud." [Aside from the lack of awareness, some announcements or information are sometimes overlooked, while others are simply not interested in attending activities.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD7: "dili man tanan accepting sa GAD." [Not everyone is accepting of GAD initiatives.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD5: "main challenge gyud is for me naay 2 factors based on my understanding naay First factor is cultural resistance. Second factor is weak of accountability." [Based on my understanding, the main challenge involves two factors. The first is cultural resistance. The second factor is weak accountability.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD6: "isa sa challeges, Kana jud nga malain sila. Kanang feel nila nga school dili supportive sa ilaha." [One of the challenges is when students feel offended or think that the school is not supportive of them.]</p>

Institutionalizing GAD Policies and Practices. This theme emerged as a significant aspect of the lived experiences of GAD advocates in higher education institutions. Advocates face the challenge of embedding gender-responsive policies into existing institutional frameworks while ensuring compliance with guidelines and standards. This requires the development and maintenance of systems and processes that consistently reflect gender sensitivity, such as incorporating gender considerations into planning, reporting, and administrative procedures. The complexity of aligning institutional practices with GAD mandates demands continuous monitoring, adjustment, and advocacy, highlighting the need for careful coordination, strategic planning, and sustained commitment. These responsibilities place considerable demands on advocates’ organizational, analytical, and collaborative skills, underscoring both the importance and the difficulty of fully institutionalizing gender and development initiatives within higher education.

The sub-theme policy integration and compliance was validated by GAD1, GAD2, GAD6, GAD7, and GAD 8. They shared that, *“About fud sa policies and practices ma’am is through gina issue na mga memorandum orders. Didtua nak indicate kung unsay mga practices. Including fud kanang mag buhat ug activity design apil fud ang culturally sensitive ug dapat naka anchor sa CHED mandate.”(GAD1)*

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[Regarding the policies and practices, ma'am, these are implemented through the issuance of memorandum orders. These indicate the specific practices to be followed, including the preparation of activity designs that are culturally sensitive and aligned with the CHED mandate.]

"As an HR officer ug in collaboration among gender and development office amoa gina follow ang mga memorandum order nga gina pagawas sa GAD office like gina categorize gyud namo according to their gender ug sex ang mga records sa amoang personnel."(GAD2)

[As an HR officer, in collaboration with the Gender and Development Office, we follow the memorandum orders issued by the GAD Office. We also categorize our personnel records according to gender and sex.]

"Sa integration sa policies kay same sa akong giingon ganina aside sa naga gamit mig sex-disaggregated data sa mga documents gina integrate fud namo sa amoang mga manuals."(GAD2)

[In terms of integrating policies, as I mentioned earlier, aside from using sex-disaggregated data in our documents, we also integrate these policies into our manuals.]

"For the gender-responsive policies and practices, we integrated this.....We have policies, and these are written in our student handbook."(GAD6)

[For gender-responsive policies and practices, we have integrated them into our institution. We also have policies that are written in our student handbook.]

"We have policies man, kay I thibk ang...its also a mandate man gud because of CMO no. 1 of the CHED. Tungud kay nay sisayay policy since it is mandated gyud na I mainstream gyud siya , so, we also have mga internal policies will anchored also sa CHED and Philippine Commission on Women (PCW) .Ana siya maong integrated gyud siya."(GAD7)

[We have policies because, I think, it is also mandated under CHED Memorandum Order (CMO) No. 1. Since there is an existing policy, it is really mandated to mainstream it. We also have internal policies that are aligned with CHED and the Philippine Commission on Women (PCW), which is why it is fully integrated.]

"Sa among school is dapat no discrimination, especially sa mga PWD students namo. NAa fud mi specific na policy sa student handbook for no discrimination in admitting the students."(GAD8)

[In our school, discrimination is not allowed, especially against our PWD students. We also have a specific policy in the student handbook regarding non-discrimination in student admission.]

Meanwhile, the sub-theme gender-responsive systems and processes was also evident as part of the experiences of the GAD advocates which were confirmed by

GAD1, GAD2, GAD3, GAD4, GAD6 and GAD8. They shared that,

"About fud sa policies and practices ma'am is through gina issue na mga memorandum orders. Didtua nak indicate kung unsay mga practices. Including fud kanang mag buhat ug activity design apil fud ang culturally sensitive ug dapat naka anchor sa CHED mandate."(GAD1)

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[For gender-responsive policies and practices, we have integrated them into our institution. We also have policies that are written in our student handbook.]

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for no discrimination in admitting the students.”(GAD8)

[In our school, discrimination is not allowed, especially against our PWD students. We also have a specific policy in the student handbook regarding non-discrimination in student admission.]

“Example sa mga gender-responsiveness strategies processes sa programs is naa man mi annual activities nga gina align fud sa Department of Health (DOH) programs. Our target population sa program is open to all gender apil nafud dihaa ang mga LGBTQ member nga students. “(GAD1)

[An example of gender-responsive strategies and processes in our programs is that we conduct annual activities aligned with the programs of the Department of Health (DOH). The target population of our programs is open to all genders, including LGBTQ members and students.]

“Sa administrative side sex-disaggregated data used sa mga documents.”(GAD2)

[On the administrative side, sex-disaggregated data are used in our documents.]

“As an instructor, gina integrate gyud nako through my teaching practices by ensuring that my teaching methods and materials are inclusive ug dili gender bias. Tapos dapat nay equal participation ang mga students and respect diversity.”(GAD3)

[As an instructor, I integrate gender responsiveness through my teaching practices by ensuring that my teaching methods and materials are inclusive and free from gender bias. There should also be equal participation among students, while respecting diversity.]

“Sa amoa is, sa mga teachers naga undergo mana silage gender- sensitivity training so, pag magtawag sila ug student amoang gina ingon sa ilaha na pinaka safe is “they or them” kana nga pronouns aron dili gyud sila malain.” (GAD4)

[In our institution, teachers undergo gender-sensitivity training. When addressing students, we encourage them to use the safest pronouns, such as “they” or “them,” to avoid offending anyone.]

“We recognize students of different sexes and gender preferences; we do not have biases. We just deal each one of them depending on their sex preferences.” (GAD6)

[We recognize students of different sexes and gender preferences, and we do not practice bias. We treat each individual according to their preferred gender identity and preferences.]

“Gina-apil namo sa sa form kung PWD sila aside ana ang freshmen na words gi ilisan namo ug ug new students aron dili gender bias. Dapat Gender Fair Language nay gamiton.”(GAD8)

[In our forms, we include an option indicating whether a student is a PWD. Aside from that, we replaced the term “freshmen” with “new students” to avoid gender bias. We are encouraged to use genderfair language.]

In addition, institutionalizing GAD policies and practices is reflected on the subtheme promotion of inclusivity and gender sensitivity which were confirmed by GAD1,

GAD2, GAD3, GAD4, and GAD5. They claimed that,

“Every December nay World Aids Day Celebration. Naay gina conduct na mga symposium aron ma aware sila sa mga risky behaviors. Maka avail ang mga students sa free HIV testing.” (GAD1)

[Every December, we celebrate World AIDS Day. We conduct symposiums to raise awareness about risky behaviors. Students are also able to avail themselves of free HIV testing.]

“During sa pag conduct ug gender-sensitivity training maka engage mis mga faculty nami. Sa students fud kanang gina respect lang fud namo sila kung unsa ilang gender.”(GAD2)

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[During the conduct of gender-sensitivity training, we engage with faculty members. As for the students, we simply ensure that their gender identities are respected.]

“Every time nga nay GAD activities or even not GAD activity always gina consider and gender equality. During classes fud gina remind ug gina encourage jud ang mga students nga be respectful to one another despite kung unsay gender identity niya.”(GAD3)
[Whenever there are GAD activities, or even in non-GAD activities, gender equality is always considered. During classes, students are constantly reminded and encouraged to be respectful toward one another regardless of gender identity.]

“Number one gyud kay ang empathy gyud nga kuan, majority man gud sa mga students karon dako kaau ang population na part sa among LGBTQ ug sa SOGIE, so, very sensitive baya jud kaau na sila sa gender. In our school naa man gud mi uniform, so, I think nay mga students nga naga transition, So, para sa amoa empathy nalang fud siguro sa mga students na supportahan sila ug e respect sila.”(GAD4)

[The most important thing is empathy. Nowadays, a large portion of our student population belongs to the LGBTQ community and SOGIE groups, and they can be very sensitive regarding gender issues. In our school, we have uniforms, and there are students who are transitioning. For us, empathy is important so that these students will feel supported and respected.]

“Naa silay mga advertisement like sa TV, naay mga educational video. Tapos tanan mga employees sa school dapat informed gyud sila. (GAD5)

[There are advertisements shown on television as well as educational videos. In addition, all school employees should be properly informed and aware of these initiatives.]

The findings show that policy integration and compliance are essential in institutionalizing Gender and Development (GAD) in educational settings. Aligning school policies with the mandates of the Commission on Higher Education helps ensure consistency and accountability. Including GAD provisions in official documents such as memorandum orders, student handbooks, and manuals reflects the institution’s commitment to gender equality. The use of sex-disaggregated data also supports informed decision-making by identifying gaps and guiding appropriate actions. Moreover, integrating GAD into instruction, research, and extension activities shows that gender concerns are part of the institution’s core functions, making implementation more sustainable.

In addition, gender-responsive systems and processes show how these policies are applied in everyday practice. Efforts such as promoting equal treatment, using inclusive language, and applying non-biased teaching materials reflect a shift from compliance to actual practice. Recognizing diverse gender identities and creating inclusive environments further demonstrate a deeper understanding of gender issues. While policies provide the framework, consistent gender-responsive practices determine the effectiveness of GAD implementation within the institution.

The findings of this study confirm that the institutionalization of Gender and Development (GAD) policies within higher education institutions (HEIs) is a key factor in mainstreaming gender initiatives. Participants emphasized that embedding gender perspectives into organizational structures, culture, and processes ensures sustainability and consistency in GAD implementation. This aligns with Hernandez et al. (2022), who found that while HEIs demonstrate commitment to GAD integration, challenges such as unclear policy frameworks and limited capacity-building activities can hinder full institutionalization. The current study validates that formal policies, handbooks, and manuals serve as structural guides, reinforcing the commitment of HEIs to gender-responsive practices.

Institutionalizing Gender and Development (GAD) policies and practices in higher education necessitates the establishment of gender-responsive systems and well-defined processes that promote inclusivity and equity in institutional operations.

According to Perez et al., successful GAD mainstreaming depends on strong institutional frameworks, committed leadership, and the systematic incorporation of gender perspectives into programs and practices. Likewise, Tanjung et al. emphasized that systems related to planning, budgeting, and governance are essential in ensuring accountability and addressing the varying gender needs within academic institutions. These viewpoints indicate that institutionalizing GAD goes beyond policy formulation, as it also requires operational systems capable of translating gender principles into daily institutional practices.

Furthermore, integrating GAD into institutional policies and ensuring compliance are crucial in maintaining the sustainability and effectiveness of GAD initiatives. Hernandez et al. explained that incorporating GAD into institutional plans, programs, and activities enhances alignment and supports consistent implementation across different units. Similarly, Palma observed that adherence to GAD policies is largely shaped by institutional support, monitoring mechanisms, and continuous capacity-building initiatives for stakeholders. Together, these studies enrich the existing body of knowledge by showing that effective GAD institutionalization relies on the interaction between policy integration and strong compliance mechanisms, highlighting the importance of strategic, coordinated, and evidence-based approaches in advancing gender equality in higher education.

Implementing GAD Programs and Strategies. This theme surfaced as a central aspect of GAD advocates’ experiences in higher education institutions. Advocates face the challenge of translating gender policies into concrete programs, requiring the organization and facilitation of trainings, seminars, and awareness initiatives that build knowledge and engagement among faculty, staff, and students. At the same time, integrating gender perspectives into the curriculum and academic activities demands careful planning,

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alignment with learning outcomes, and continuous monitoring to ensure meaningful and sustained impact. These responsibilities often involve coordinating multiple initiatives, managing logistical and instructional demands, and balancing stakeholder expectations, highlighting both the importance and the complexity of implementing GAD programs effectively within institutional contexts.

GAD1, GAD2, GAD3, GAD4, GAD5, GAD6, and GAD 8 affirmed that they long for trainings, seminars, and awareness programs relevant to GAD. This contention strengthened the sub-theme, stating that:

“Example sa mga strategies ug mga programs is naa man mi annual activities like symposiums, trainings, and orientation nga gina align fud sa DOH programs.” (GAD1)

[Examples of our strategies and programs include annual activities such as symposiums, trainings, and orientations that are aligned with the programs of the Department of Health (DOH).]

“Sa among mga personnel peronnel fud dapat maka undergo sila ug Gender Sensitivity Training aron naay silay background knowledge kung unsa ang GAD ug unsaon pag mainstream ang GAD. Isa sa highlight dria is ang pag conduct ug training sa amoang mga school guards since sila man gyud naay first encounter sa mga tao na musulod sa school, so, dapat capacitated sila.” (GAD2)

[Our personnel are also required to undergo Gender Sensitivity Training so that they will have background knowledge about GAD and how to mainstream it. One of the highlights of this initiative is the conduct of training for our school guards since they are usually the first people to encounter individuals entering the school. Therefore, it is important that they are properly capacitated.]

“As a support system sa GAD office naga tabang mi conduct sa mga GAD activities like Women’s month kanang naay mga pa contest sa amoang mga students.” (GAD3)

[As a support system for the GAD Office, we help conduct GAD-related activities such as Women’s Month celebrations, including contests and other engaging activities for students.]

“Sa amoa, we conduct seminars aside from that not just with students but also our faculties and staff and mas strong amoang mag mainstream sa gender and development sa amoang security personnel. Kay sila man gud ang first hand na makakita gyud sa mga students. I had conducted sa Training with our personnel in the university sa tanan na branches. I share a same dilemma because kay students man fud ko nila before.” (GAD4)

[In our institution, we conduct seminars not only for students but also for faculty members and staff. We also strongly mainstream Gender and Development among our security personnel because they are the first to interact with students. I personally conducted training sessions with our personnel across all university branches. I share the same dilemma because those students were also once my students.]

“we have a lot of gender activities, aside from that syempre awareness sa mga students through kanang posters. Tapos naa fud mi mga symposiums. Naga handle sa amoa is the GAD office gyud. Ang GAD Office sa main campus sila ang naga anhe diria.” (GAD5)

[We have many gender-related activities. Aside from that, we also raise awareness among students through posters and symposiums. The GAD Office handles these initiatives, and the personnel from the main campus usually visit our campus to conduct the activities.]

“I am not really particular on the individual programs but in the GAD office gina invite fud mi every naay activity nga naka focus sa men ug women. Katung mga seminars on Sexual Harassment, katung safe spaces act and others.” (GAD6)

[I am not very particular with the individual programs, but the GAD Office regularly invites us whenever there are activities focused on men and women, such as seminars on Sexual Harassment, the Safe Spaces Act, and other related topics.]

“sa among school mam we have activities like GAD trainings and seminars. Dihaa namo ma socialize ang matag-usa. Naga conduct mi ug women’s month and other GAD-related activities which is mandated fud sa CHED.” (GAD8)

[In our school, we conduct activities such as GAD trainings and seminars where everyone is encouraged to socialize and participate. We also celebrate Women’s Month and conduct other GAD-related activities, which are mandated by CHED.]

Moreover, the sub-theme curriculum and academic integration was reinforced by GAD2, GAD3, GAD7, and GAD9. They asserted that,

“As an instructor, naka teach man gyud kog gender and society nga subject or even in other subjects na akong na handle gina promote gyud nako ang gender equality as it one of the objectives sa GAD.” (GAD3)

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[As an instructor, I teach the subject Gender and Society, and even in the other subjects that I handle, I always promote gender equality since it is one of the objectives of GAD.]

“Dili kaau ko familiar sa academic nga side kay dili man ako ang focal sa GAD, but, as far as I remember integrated na sa mga subjects example sa Psy 101 the understanding the self. (GAD2)

[I am not very familiar with the academic side because I am not the focal person for GAD. However, as far as I can remember, GAD concepts are already integrated into subjects such as Psy 101 the Understanding the Self.]

“Example in the instruction we have part GAD sa pag analyze, or pag critic, sa mga proposed curriculum. We also have subject on gender and society that is specific the subject on gender. So, we produce instructional materials on that. So, that’s on the instruction. Sa research naman, we establish GEDSI center that is also under GAD gihapon kay focus man siya on gender studies ang gina conduct, and then as well as on the extension. We use tool na katong, harmonize GAD (Harmonized Gender and Development Guidelines) katong to mainstream it in terms of budget or in terms of the activities.”(GAD7)

[For example, in instruction, GAD is included in the analysis and evaluation of proposed curricula. We also offer a subject on Gender and Society that specifically focuses on gender concerns, and we produce instructional materials for it. In terms of research, we established a GEDSI Center, which is still under GAD because it focuses on conducting gender studies. The same integration is also applied in extension programs. We use tools such as the Harmonized Gender and Development Guidelines (HGDD) to mainstream GAD in terms of budgeting and implementation of activities]

“Kung sa instruction fud, we have gender and society nga karon, which, this subject is specific for gender. In fact, currently, we are reviewing our curriculum base sa new release na gender-responsive assessment tool sa CHED.”(GAD9)

[In terms of instruction, we currently offer the subject Gender and Society, which specifically focuses on gender issues. In fact, we are presently reviewing our curriculum based on the newly released Gender-Responsive Assessment Tool from CHED.]

In addition, the sub-theme development of inclusive instructional practices was strengthened by GAD3, GAD5, and GAD7. They believed that,

“Gina ensure gyud nako that my teaching methods and materials are inclusive ug walay gender bias. Otherwise in administrative function I will see to it that I am complying the GAD related memos like I will become a bridge if ever naay mga harassment dapat kabalo ko unsay process sa mga referral system. “(GAD3)

[I ensure that my teaching methods and materials are inclusive and free from gender bias. In terms of administrative functions, I also make sure that I comply with GAD-related memoranda. I serve as a bridge whenever there are cases of harassment by being knowledgeable about the proper referral system and processes.]

“For example I am more conscious on paano ko mo lihok, I am more conscious on how other people also act and treat other people. Kanang hala tama ba kaha ni akong pagahimoon , dili ba kaha ko maka offend sa lain. “(GAD5)

[For example, I have become more conscious about how I act and how other people treat one another. I always reflect on whether my actions are appropriate and whether they might offend others.]

“Since part si GAD sa pag critic sa tanan, we produce instructional materials on that, that is inclusive from what we observe sa community na pwedi namo na basis.”(GAD7)

[Since GAD is part of the evaluation and critique process in all areas, we produce instructional materials that are inclusive and based on what we observe in the community, which can serve as our basis.]

The findings indicate that trainings, seminars, and awareness programs are essential in strengthening the implementation of Gender and Development (GAD) within institutions. The expressed need for gender sensitivity trainings, symposiums, and activities such as World AIDS Day and Women’s Month highlights the importance of continuous capacity-building among employees and stakeholders. These initiatives serve as platforms for increasing awareness, correcting misconceptions, and promoting shared understanding of gender-related issues. They also address critical topics such as sexual harassment and safe spaces, which are vital in creating a secure and respectful institutional environment. Furthermore, the inclusion of community extension programs shows that GAD efforts extend beyond the institution, fostering social responsibility and community engagement. These activities suggest that effective GAD implementation requires not only policies but also sustained educational efforts that build knowledge, awareness, and commitment among individuals.

In addition, the integration of GAD into the curriculum and academic processes reflects a deeper and more sustainable approach to promoting gender equality. Offering subjects such as Gender and Society, embedding GAD concepts in classroom discussions, and using inclusive instructional materials demonstrate how gender perspectives are incorporated into teaching and learning. The inclusion of GAD in curriculum review processes ensures that gender responsiveness is systematically considered in academic planning and development. Encouraging gender-related research further supports the generation of knowledge and evidence that can inform institutional practices and policies. These efforts show that GAD is not treated as an add-on but as an integral part of academic

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life. Curriculum integration and academic initiatives help shape students' perspectives, making them more aware, critical, and responsive to gender issues in both educational and societal contexts.

Implementing Gender and Development (GAD) programs and strategies in higher education would significantly involve the integration of gender perspectives into the curriculum and academic processes. As explained by Hernandez et al. (2021), embedding GAD in institutional programs, activities, and academic plans ensures that gender concepts are reflected in teaching, learning, and research functions, thereby strengthening institutional commitment to gender equality.

Similarly, Manuel (2024) emphasized that higher education institutions serve as key spaces for shaping gender awareness, highlighting the importance of incorporating gender-sensitive content into classroom instruction to promote inclusive learning environments. In support, Cagang et al. (2023) found that integrating gender-sensitive pedagogical practices within teacher education enhances students' awareness and application of gender principles, contributing to more responsive and inclusive academic systems. These studies contribute to the body of knowledge by demonstrating that curriculum and academic integration are essential mechanisms for sustaining GAD implementation and fostering gender-responsive education.

Moreover, training, seminars, and awareness programs are critical strategies in strengthening GAD implementation within institutions. Palma (2025) highlighted that awareness and understanding of GAD concepts significantly influence the effectiveness and satisfaction of program implementation, indicating the need for continuous education and capacity-building initiatives. Likewise, Villegas et al. (2023) emphasized the development of training modules for GAD focal persons, underscoring the importance of structured learning interventions in enhancing gender sensitivity and institutional capability. Furthermore, Gil (2021) noted that regular seminars, workshops, and GAD-related activities increase stakeholder engagement and promote active participation in gender advocacy within higher education institutions. These studies enrich the existing body of knowledge by affirming that sustained training and awareness programs are vital components of effective GAD strategies, as they build competencies, improve participation, and ensure the continuous advancement of gender equality initiatives in education.

Collaborating and Engaging with Stakeholders. This theme emerged as a critical aspect of the lived experiences of GAD advocates in higher education institutions. Advocates navigate the complexities of engaging multiple stakeholders, including faculty, staff, and students, while also coordinating with various offices and external partners to ensure the successful implementation of GAD initiatives. Limited participation or varying levels of commitment among stakeholders can hinder program effectiveness, requiring advocates to employ strategies that foster collaboration, build shared ownership, and maintain consistent communication. Additionally, sustaining inter-office and external partnerships demands careful planning, negotiation, and alignment of goals across different units and organizations.

The sub-theme inter-office and external collaboration was highlighted by GAD1, GAD2, GAD3, GAD4, and GAD9. They stressed that,

"Makipag collaborate mi sa City health office aron didtua mi magkuha ug mga speaker. Usahay man fud gud naga offer sila kung naa silay available snacks. Ug sa other offices fud diria sa school like naga tap fud mi sa GAd office aron ma supply yan mi kung unsay need namo. Other one also usahay mo tap mis Supreme Student Council (SSC) like sila mo provide sa mga token. Collaboration jud siya mam dako kaau siyag tabang kung daghan mo lend ug help aron maging successful ang mga program and activities."(GAD1)

[We collaborate with the City Health Office so that we can invite speakers from their office. Sometimes, they also offer available snacks for the activities. We also coordinate with other offices in the school, such as the GAD Office, to provide the materials and support that we need. At times, we also tap the Supreme Student Council (SSC), especially when they can provide tokens. Collaboration is really important, ma'am, because having many people willing to help greatly contributes to the success of programs and activities.]

"It gives us perseverance. Samot na sa collaboration makatabang siya aron dili kaau dali ta ma stress kay dghan man committees, do daghan mutabang sa mga lihokon aron ma realize ang program or activity kay tinabangay man."(GAD2)

[It gives us perseverance. Collaboration is especially helpful because it lessens stress since there are many committees involved. Many people help accomplish the tasks, making it easier to realize and implement programs and activities because everyone works together.]

"Dapat Collaboration gyud, kay aron ma ensures that GAD initiatives are not dependent on individual effort alone. Working with colleagues helps me distribute responsibilities even amid workload pressures. Through support system it reinforces long-term engagement." (GAD3)

[There should really be collaboration because it ensures that GAD initiatives are not dependent on individual effort alone. Working with colleagues helps distribute responsibilities even amid workload pressures. Through a support system, it also reinforces long-term engagement.]

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“Every Semester naga meeting mi sabay ang drug free meeting sa tanan branches, aron mahibal-an ug unsay update unsay progress para kung unsa poy nag work sa other branches kay pwedi ma apply sa amoang school if its applicable.”(GAD4)

[Every semester, we conduct meetings together with the Drug-Free Program meetings across all branches so that we can identify updates and monitor progress. We also learn what strategies work in other branches, which we may apply in our own school if they are applicable.]

“Then, ang collaboration fud effective gyud siya kay naa may division of work. Kanang naka committee na siya. Ang pina importante ang support sa administration kay unsaon mana imong mga targets kung dili ka I approved sa college president/administrator.”(GAD9)

[Collaboration is truly effective because there is a clear division of work through committee assignments. Most importantly, administrative support is essential because targets and plans cannot be implemented without the approval of the college president or administrator.]

In addition, the sub-theme participation of faculty, staff, and students was emphasized by GAD1, GAD3 GAD4, and GAD8 They highlighted that,

“kanang gina encourage jud namo mga students kanang gina ingnan namo ang mga program heads kung pwedi ma inform ang mga students through group chat nila aron ma inform ug ma aware sila kung unsa ang mga services nga gina offer namo sa clinic. Para ma promote ang gender equality pwedi kaaug sila mo avail regardless sa gender. Then, we have also blood letting , gina encourage gyud namo participation nga open for all.”(GAD1)

[We strongly encourage students to participate by coordinating with program heads and requesting them to inform students through their group chats. This helps make students aware of the services offered by the clinic. To promote gender equality, everyone is encouraged to avail themselves of these services regardless of gender. We also conduct bloodletting activities, and participation is open to all.]

“During naay training dihaa mi maka engage mis nga faculty ug sa students. Ug dapat ang mga students mo join jud sila kay para rman fud nis ilaha.”(GAD2)

[During trainings, we are able to engage with both faculty members and students. Students are also encouraged to participate because these programs are intended for their benefit.]

“ Aside sa gina encourage namo ang mga students nga mo participate sa discussion or any activity ug walay bias sa ilang gender. Dapat Ipa feel gyud sa ilaha mga accept sila samot natung mga LGBT aron dili maulaw. Pero, so far, mas active paman gani ang mga LGBT hinoon. “(GAD3)

[Aside from encouraging students to participate in discussions and activities without gender bias, we also make sure that they feel accepted, especially members of the LGBT community, so that they will not feel shy or excluded. In fact, LGBT students are often among the most active participants.]

“ ang staff noon aware ko since part man ko sa staff sa non-teaching personnel. Naga adtu mi or naa mi community na gi adopt, didtua mi permi naga seminar. We provide GAD development seminar sa ilaha aside sa financial literacy. Isa gyud na sa ways namo aron ma engage among mga staff.” (GAD4)

[As part of the non-teaching personnel, I am aware that our staff members are actively engaged in community activities. We regularly visit our adopted community where we conduct GAD development seminars in addition to financial literacy seminars. This is one of the ways we engage our staff members.]

“ Everytime naay mga activity sa school, dhaa fud mi mahatagan ug time aron ma socialize ang mga personnel. Kanang naay mga meeting fud and other activity sa school.” (GAD8)

[Whenever there are school activities, we are also given opportunities to socialize with other personnel. This usually happens during meetings and other school-related activities.]

Moreover, as part of the main theme collaborating and engaging with stakeholder, the sub-theme promotion of inclusive participation and support was attested by GAD1, GAD4, GAD5 and GAD6. They pointed out that, *“tanan activity namo is open for all gender same anang sa blood letting activity ug HIV testing.” (GAD1)*

[All of our activities are open to all genders, such as bloodletting activities and HIV testing.]

“aron ma encourage sila na mo participate we need to respect lang gyud kung unsa sila.” (GAD6)

[To encourage participation, we simply need to respect individuals for who they are.]

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We make sure that the activity was enjoyable and we have to make sure it was safe for them and , so far, mao man gyud ang makita sa mga students maong mo join gyud sila. Every school mana namo gina conduct gyud. Tungud siguro kay makita nila nga lingaw siya and makit nila nga it is safe for them. (GAD4)

[We make sure that the activities are enjoyable and safe for the students. So far, this is what students notice, which is why they willingly participate. We conduct these activities in every school because students see that they are enjoyable and safe for them.]

“dapat fully inform sila ug dapat I follow-up fud aron muattend gyud sila to any GAD activity.” (GAD5)

[Participants should be fully informed and consistently followed up to ensure that they attend GAD-related activities.]

The findings indicate that inter-office coordination and external collaboration are key factors in the effective implementation of Gender and Development (GAD) programs. Partnerships with external entities such as the City Health Office, along with cooperation among various internal units, demonstrate a shared and collective effort in addressing gender-related concerns. Collaboration among student organizations, administrative offices, and GAD units ensures that responsibilities are distributed, leading to more efficient program implementation. The presence of committees and interdepartmental coordination further reflects a structured system that supports both planning and execution. Overall, these collaborative mechanisms show that GAD implementation is not confined to a single office but requires the active engagement of multiple stakeholders within and outside the institution to achieve more sustainable and far-reaching outcomes.

In addition, the involvement of faculty, staff, and students significantly enhances the effectiveness of GAD initiatives. Approaches such as mobilizing student participation through program heads and communication channels, as well as mandating involvement through memorandum orders, demonstrate deliberate efforts to strengthen engagement. Trainings and seminars provide opportunities for participation while simultaneously increasing awareness and understanding of gender-related issues. The emphasis on recognizing and respecting students' gender identities fosters an inclusive environment that promotes diversity and acceptance. Moreover, the provision of incentives serves as a motivational strategy that encourages continued participation in GAD activities. These findings suggest that meaningful and sustained engagement from all members of the academic community is vital to ensuring that GAD programs are not only implemented but also integrated into everyday institutional practices.

Collaborating and engaging with stakeholders would be a crucial component in the effective implementation of Gender and Development (GAD) programs in higher education, particularly through inter-office and external partnerships. As highlighted by Perez et al. (2025), stakeholder engagement models such as faculty committees, student-led organizations, and community partnerships strengthen GAD mainstreaming by promoting shared responsibility and extending program impact beyond institutional boundaries.

Similarly, Aloba et al. (2024) emphasized that effective coordination among offices and external stakeholders is necessary to address gaps in program implementation, noting that limited collaboration and unclear communication can hinder the success of GAD initiatives . Supporting this, Albaladejo (2020) identified limited institutional collaboration as a key challenge in GAD implementation, underscoring the need for stronger linkages and cooperative efforts among institutions and agencies to sustain gender-responsive programs . These studies contribute to the body of knowledge by demonstrating that collaborative structures are essential in ensuring coherent, inclusive, and sustainable GAD practices.

Moreover, the active participation of faculty, staff, and students would significantly enhance the effectiveness of GAD initiatives. Perigo and Mangila (2020) found that GAD implementation varies across stakeholders, highlighting the importance of inclusive participation in planning, implementation, and evaluation processes. In the same vein, Abalajon et al. (2023) emphasized that awareness and involvement of faculty, staff, and students are critical in promoting gender equality and ensuring that GAD concepts are translated into actual institutional practices.

Additionally, Dimas et al. (2020) stressed that strengthening stakeholder involvement, particularly among students and community members, is necessary to improve GAD awareness and engagement within educational institutions. These studies enrich the existing body of knowledge by affirming that meaningful participation of all academic stakeholders is fundamental to the successful implementation and sustainability of GAD programs in higher education.

Experiencing Challenges in GAD Implementation. This theme emerged as a significant aspect of the lived experiences of GAD advocates in higher education institutions. Advocates face limitations in financial and material resources, which restrict the scope and reach of gender and development initiatives, often requiring creative solutions to maximize impact with minimal support. In addition, challenges related to scheduling, varying levels of awareness, and occasional resistance from stakeholders further complicate the implementation process, making it difficult to achieve consistent participation and engagement. These constraints highlight the multifaceted nature of mainstreaming GAD, where advocates must navigate logistical, institutional, and cultural barriers while striving to advance gender-responsive practices effectively within the academe.

This main theme comprised of resource and budget constraints which were affirmed by GAD1, GAD 2, GAD3, and GAD9. Meanwhile, the sub-theme scheduling and time constraints was one of the challenges in the GAD implementation and this

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was backed up by GAD2, GAD3, GAD5 and GAD9. They underscored that, *In addition, since under man gyud mis LGU ug gina bahin-bahin lng fud ang budget ug limited lng gyud siya. Halimbawa kung naay activity need man gyud naay budget, kung mo provide tag snacks, so dapat mo sort nalang fud ta kung asa dapita ta maka barato. Pero mas nindot man gud unta kung naay budget na dako dako aron ma providan fud ang atung mga participants para ma feel fud nila nga comfortable fud sila.*” (GAD1)

[In addition, since we are under the LGU, the budget is divided and is quite limited. For example, if an activity requires a budget for snacks, we have to find ways to source more affordable options. However, it would be better if we had a larger budget so that we could provide more for the participants and help them feel more comfortable.]

“Kasagaran gyud kay ang scheduling sa meeting tungud kay usahay naga overlap ang mga meeting ug activity dapat paunhanay ug pa approve sa director sa schedule. Ikaduha, kay kulang sa budget.” (GAD2)

[One common challenge is scheduling meetings because activities sometimes overlap. Schedules need to be properly coordinated and approved by the director. Another issue is the limited budget.]

“Mga challenges is unang-una time and workload constraints. Tungud kay Integrating gender-responsive approaches into lesson planning, sa mga teaching strategies, and classroom activities usahay maglisod ko aside lng gyud atung mga subject mga dali I integrate like Understanding the self. And tungud sa limited resources tungud kay gina bahin-bahin raman ang budget maong limited rafud ang pwedi ma conduct nga activity. Usahay fud, lack of awareness naa man gud usahay tungud sa ka busy ma misslook ang mga information kay sa amoa man gud kasagaran through GC I post ang mga updates. Human sa kadghan ug updates matabunan ng uban.” (GAD3)

[The main challenges include time and workload constraints. Integrating gender-responsive approaches into lesson planning, teaching strategies, and classroom activities can be difficult, especially with other subjects that are easier to integrate, like Understanding the Self. Another challenge is the limited resources because the budget is divided, which limits the number of activities that can be conducted. Sometimes, there is also a lack of awareness since information is usually posted in group chats, and important updates can be missed due to the volume of messages.]

“cguro, Kung naay enough budget, collaboration, and specially support sa administration. Because, daghan man gud kag ma realize na mga programs ug activities kung naay budget, kay for example. Kung naay activity sa gawas, need gyud transportation, foods, materials ug uban pa.” (GAD9)

[If there is sufficient budget, strong collaboration, and especially administrative support, many programs and activities can be successfully implemented. With adequate funding, activities outside the school such as transportation, food, and materials can be properly provided.]

“Kanang usahay naay dungan nga activity i conduct sa school.” (GAD5)

[Sometimes, there are activities that are conducted simultaneously within the school.]

“Kuan kanang sa Budget gyud, since kung naay need na mga policies na himoon need fud na e convine ang mga administrator or ang TWG, so, need fud ug budget, samot nag outside the school ang venue. Kay base sa akong experience mas nindot gyud e conduct ang activity like seminar outside sa school kay mas maka fucos gyud ang participants unlike kung within sa school ra. Daghan kaau mga concerns na dili malikayan. Aside ana, kanang usahay naay mga overlapping activities imbis naka plan out naka then need nafud e adjust ang schedule.” (GAD9)

[The main concern is really the budget. When there is a need to formulate or implement policies, administrators or the Technical Working Group (TWG) need to convene, and this requires funding. Budget is also needed especially when the venue is outside the school. Based on my experience, it is better to conduct seminars outside the school because participants are more focused compared to when activities are held within the campus. However, many concerns cannot be avoided. Another issue is overlapping activities—sometimes even if everything is already planned, schedules still need to be adjusted.]

Furthermore, GAD3, GAD 4, GAD5, GAD6, and GAD7 claimed the sub-theme awareness and resistance as part of the challenge in the GAD implementation. The stressed that,

“Ang uban aside sa lack of awareness, ma mislook ang announcement or information, naa fud uban dili ganahan mo attend gyud.” (GAD3)

[Aside from the lack of awareness, some announcements or information are sometimes overlooked, while others are simply not interested in attending activities.]

dili man tanan accepting sa GAD. In fairness sa akoang mga kauban naka accept rman fud sila, though naa gyuy uban na dili maka accept dayun, pero tungud kay para sa college mo follow gyud sila.” (GAD7)

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[Not everyone is accepting of GAD initiatives. However, to be fair, most of my colleagues have accepted them. Although there are still some who are not immediately accepting, they still comply because it is part of the college policies and programs.]

“main challenge gyud is for me naay 2 factors based on my understanding naay First factor id cultural resistance kay dili man gud tanan tao kay open in adapting the Gender Sensitivity, sometimes they sanctify nila ilang culture some religious view gina take negative nila .maong sometimes dili sila mo join kay conflict sa ilang views or values. Second factor is weak of accountability , some people are think na they are not accountable in terms of learning or accepting of this kind of discussion kay dili man tanan open for now to acknowledge what Gender and development is.” (GAD5)

[Based on my understanding, the main challenge involves two factors. The first is cultural resistance because not everyone is open to adapting gender sensitivity concepts. Some people strongly uphold their culture or religious beliefs and may view these negatively. As a result, they sometimes choose not to participate because they feel that these discussions conflict with their values and beliefs. The second factor is weak accountability. Some individuals think that they are not responsible for learning about or accepting these kinds of discussions because not everyone is currently open to understanding what Gender and Development truly means.]

“Actually we have different challenges and we have different reaction from different of students, kana laging naay biases sa gender. Nganong tagaan daw ug bili ang mga LGBT. Kanang ngano daw dili hatagan ug chance ang mga LGBT na mag cross dress.Asida ana kanang they request nga mag gamit ug girl name nila.. Mao na ang mga challenges.” (GAD6)

[We encounter different challenges and reactions from students, especially regarding gender biases. Some students question why importance is given to LGBT individuals, while others ask why LGBT students are not allowed to cross-dress. There are also requests from students who prefer to use female names. These are some of the challenges we face.]

isa sa challenges, Kana jud nga malain sila. Kanang feel nila nga ang school dili supportive sa ilaha. Then again gina pasabot rafud namo sa ilaha since rules is rules sa institution man so dapat po abide sila.” (GAD4)

[One of the challenges is when students feel offended or think that the school is not supportive of them. However, we explain to them that institutional rules must still be followed because rules are part of the school policies.]

The findings reveal that resource and budget constraints are significant challenges in the implementation of Gender and Development (GAD) programs. Limited funding restricts the ability of institutions to organize activities, provide necessary materials, and sustain regular meetings and initiatives. The reliance on local government support, such as from the Local Government Unit, further affects how resources are allocated, often resulting in competing priorities. As a result, some planned programs may be reduced in scope or not fully implemented. These constraints highlight the importance of adequate and consistent financial support to ensure that GAD initiatives are carried out effectively. Without sufficient resources, even wellplanned programs may struggle to achieve their intended outcomes.

In addition, scheduling conflicts, limited awareness, and resistance to GAD are presented as ongoing challenges in its implementation. Overlapping academic and program schedules often reduce participation, as students and staff must prioritize academic responsibilities. At the same time, information overload can lead to low awareness, where important GAD messages are overlooked or not fully understood. Resistance or lack of acceptance of GAD concepts also indicates that not all stakeholders are fully engaged or supportive, which can hinder program success. Some students may even feel unsupported if policies are not clearly communicated or properly implemented. These challenges suggest that beyond resources, institutions must also focus on effective communication, proper scheduling, and continuous awareness-building to encourage greater acceptance and participation in GAD initiatives.

The findings of this study confirm that challenges in GAD implementation remain a significant barrier to effective gender mainstreaming in higher education institutions (HEIs). Participants reported difficulties such as limited institutional support, insufficient training, inadequate resources, unsustainable program implementation, and lack of clear GAD vision, all of which impede the consistent execution of gender and development initiatives. These observations aligned with Gil (2021), who noted that private HEIs in Tacloban City face issues with budget allocation, program interventions, and GAD office functions, resulting in incomplete or inconsistent implementation. Similarly, Galamgam et al. (2021) found that basic education institutions struggled to implement all five areas of the Gender Responsive Basic Education Policy, with only learners’ development and learning delivery being fully operational.

Moreover, the study confirms prior research emphasizing the critical role of GAD advocates, who often encounter barriers such as resistance to change, lack of leadership commitment, and limited professional development opportunities. Mihrete (2021) reported that Ethiopian universities face similar challenges due to the absence of dedicated gender focal persons and insufficient training, highlighting the need for institutional support and capacity building.

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In the Philippine context, Palma (2025) found that awareness of GAD concepts and laws among staff and students was limited, while implementation and satisfaction levels were moderate, indicating the need for stronger advocacy and structured programs. Hernandez et al. (2022) also emphasized that even when GAD policies exist, inadequate funding and institutional commitment hinder sustainable implementation. These findings underscore that overcoming resource, training, and structural barriers is essential to ensure the effective and continuous mainstreaming of GAD in HEIs. Figure 2 shows the Lived Experiences of GAD advocates in mainstreaming gender and development within HEI.

Figure 3. Lived Experiences of GAD Advocates in Mainstreaming Gender and Development within HEI

Coping Mechanism of GAD Advocates on the Challenges in Mainstreaming Gender and Development within HEI

The coping mechanisms of GAD advocates in mainstreaming gender and development within higher education institutions revolve around five key strategies: adaptive learning and flexibility, collaboration and support systems, personal coping and emotional regulation, strategic planning and organizational, and advocacy through training and awareness. Advocates exercise adaptive learning and flexibility by adjusting their approaches to align with evolving institutional demands, stakeholder needs, and situational challenges, allowing them to sustain effective GAD initiatives despite constraints. Collaboration and support systems provide critical resources, guidance, and shared problem-solving through networks of colleagues, administrators, and external partners, fostering a sense of collective responsibility and resilience.

Meanwhile, personal coping and emotional regulation help advocates manage stress, maintain focus, and sustain motivation, ensuring continued engagement in gender-responsive work. Strategic planning and organizational skills enable advocates to structure

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initiatives, prioritize tasks, and navigate logistical complexities efficiently. Finally, advocacy through training and awareness serves both as a coping mechanism and a proactive approach, equipping stakeholders with knowledge, addressing resistance, and promoting participation to strengthen the integration of GAD across institutional processes. These mechanisms allow advocates to navigate challenges while advancing gender mainstreaming effectively within the academe. Table 2 highlighted the coping mechanisms of GAD advocates including the main themes, sub-themes, and significant statements.

Table 2. Coping Mechanism of GAD Advocates on the Challenges in Mainstreaming

Main Theme	Sub-Theme	Significant Statements
Adapting through Learning and Flexibility	Continuous Learning and Skill Adaptation	<p>IDI-GAD1: “Hantud gyud nga naa nay gender naay LGBTQ. Pero kadugayan naka adapt raman fud mam kay everything pwedi raman siya ma learn...”</p> <p>[“Eventually, gender categories included LGBTQ individuals as well. Over time, we were able to adapt because everything can be learned.”]</p>
	Positive Acceptance of Institutional Change	<p>IDI-GAD2: “Karon, wala nman ky naka adapt nman, tapos thankful baya fud mi kay maka avail among program kay naa may budget ang GAD, 5% baya na siya.”</p> <p>[Now, it is no longer difficult because we have already adapted. We are also thankful because our programs can benefit from GAD since it has a budget allocation of 5%.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD9: “sa hinay.hinay na overcome raman fud na mga challenges.”</p> <p>[Gradually, those challenges were overcome.]</p>
	Adaptive and Resourceful Professional Practices	<p>IDI-GAD3: “I always practice sensitivity and flexibility in my teaching approach. Even it makes difficult to consistently integrate GAD perspectives across different subjects but as an instructor I need to be resourceful.”</p> <p>[I always practice sensitivity and flexibility in my teaching approach. Even though it is difficult to consistently integrate GAD perspectives across different subjects, as an instructor, I need to be resourceful.]</p>
Collaborating and Building Support Systems	Inter-Office Collaboration	<p>ODI-GAD2: “Makipag collaborate sa lain office aron ma realize ang program.”</p> <p>[I collaborate with other offices to help realize the program.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD6: “Dili kaau dali ta ma stress kay dghan man committees din daghan mutabang sa mga lihokon aron ma realize ang program or activity kay tinabangay man.”</p> <p>[We do not get stressed easily because there are many committees and many people helping with the tasks to realize the program or activity since everyone works together.]</p>
	Collaborative Partnership	<p>(GAD 9) “Nagkuha gyud kog mga GAD experts as resource speaker.”</p>

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Main Theme	Sub-Theme	Significant Statements
		<p>["I really invite GAD experts as resource speakers."]</p> <p>IDI-GAD5: "Linkages like sa mga other institutions like sa LGUS , we have also from NGOs nga naga advocate sila ana nga activities." (GAD 5)</p> <p>[Linkages with other institutions such as LGUs are important. We also receive support from NGOs that advocate for these kinds of activities.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD4; "we partner with the government here and naga invite mig mga experts...."</p> <p>[We partner with the government and invite experts.]</p>
	Collective Support Systems	<p>IDI-GAD1: "Sa akua mam mas napadali siya or nagaan ang implementation sa program ug na meet ang mga goals na gina target through collaboration, support networks ug professional development. "</p> <p>[For me, ma'am, the implementation of the program became easier and faster, and the targeted goals were achieved through collaboration, support networks, and professional development.]</p>
Managing Personal Coping and Emotional Regulation	Emotional Resilience and Positive Coping	<p>IDI-GAD8: "but, as always be patient lang gyud ko ky part man isa trabaho."</p> <p>[but I remain patient because it is part of the job.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD4: "Hinoon hawod manko mag compartmentalize, kung naay mga situation mga lisod, dili ra kaau ko makaingon nga affected ko. Kay all problems have solutions. "</p> <p>[Fortunately, I am good at compartmentalizing. When there are difficult situations, I cannot really say that I am deeply affected because I believe that all problems have solutions.]</p>
	Respectful and Growth Oriented Perspectives	<p>IDI-GAD2; "Since gina promote man gyud dria ang gender equality need to respect one another."</p> <p>[Since gender equality is actively promoted here, there is a need to respect one another.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD5: "Kanang dghan kaau kog learnings. For example I am more conscious on paano ko mo lihoc, I am more conscious on how other people also act and treat other people".</p> <p>[I have gained so many learnings. For example, I have become more conscious of how I act, and I am also more aware of how other people behave and treat others.]</p> <p>IDI-GAD4: "From doing counseling I also want a school sa better place for them."</p> <p>[Through counseling, I also want a better school environment for them.]</p>

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Main Theme	Sub-Theme	Significant Statements
Planning and Organizing GAD Implementation	Organized and Responsive Institutional Practices	<p>IDI-GAD1: “Base sa amoa, naga logbook man mi then gina isa.isa lang gyud ug ihap.”</p> <p>[Answer: Based on our practice, we record everything in a logbook and count them one by one.]</p>
	Planning and Contingency Strategies	<p>IDI-GAD9: “Dili raman sa ingon nga naka affect siya, but the only thing I can do is to have more patience lang gyud cguro. Every plan activity dapat naay gyud Plan B if ever naay mga changes sa schedule dali raka maka adapt ug iwas stress pa.”</p> <p>[It did not really affect me in a negative way, but the only thing I can do is probably to have more patience. Every planned activity should always have a Plan B in case there are sudden changes in the schedule, so that you can easily adapt and avoid stress.]</p>
	Policy Compliance	<p>IDI-GAD2: “amoa gina follow ang mga memorandum order nga gina pagawas sa GAD office.”</p> <p>[We follow the memorandum orders issued by the GAD office.]</p>
	Time and Schedule Management	<p>IDI-GAD9: “ target planning with other offices aron ma plan out daan ang mga calendar of activities.”</p> <p>[Targeted planning with other offices should be done so that the calendar of activities can already be planned ahead.]</p>
Promoting Advocacy through Training and Awareness	Continuous Capacity Building	<p>IDI-GAD3: “continuous capacity-building aron ma enhance ang integration sa mga GAD programs.”</p> <p>[continuous capacity-building to further enhance the integration of GAD programs.]</p>
	Information Dissemination	<p>IDI-GAD5: “Provide all the information needed aron muattend sila. Since it is institutional activies man gyud either they like it or not dapat mo join jud sila.”</p> <p>[Provide all the information they need so they can attend. Since these are institutional activities, whether they like it or not, they are really required to participate.]</p>
	Benchmarking Best Practices	<p>IDI-GAD9: “Nag benchmark mi sa lain school nga kadtung naa na bitaw na GAD awards and naa nay mga best practices sa GAD.”</p> <p>[I initiated benchmarking activities. We benchmarked with other schools that already had GAD awards and established best practices in GAD.]</p>
	Awareness and Perspective Change	<p>IDI-GAD2: “makahatag baya siyag enlightenment kay una baya lahi baya gyud ang definition sa babae ug lalaki.”</p> <p>[It can provided enlightenment because before, my understanding of the definitions of women and men was very different.]</p>

Adapting through Learning and Flexibility. GAD advocates in higher education institutions employ Adaptive Learning and Flexibility as a key coping mechanism to navigate the challenges of mainstreaming gender and development. This approach involves

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continuous learning and skill adaptation, allowing advocates to update their knowledge and refine strategies in response to evolving policies, stakeholder needs, and institutional priorities. Openness to change enables them to embrace new ideas, methodologies, and perspectives, fostering a proactive attitude toward overcoming obstacles. Flexibility in teaching practices allows advocates to integrate gender-responsive concepts into diverse academic contexts, adjusting instructional approaches to suit varying learner needs and institutional settings. Additionally, resourcefulness in implementation empowers advocates to maximize available materials, tools, and support systems, ensuring that GAD initiatives are carried out effectively despite limited resources or logistical constraints. GAD1, GAD2, GAD 3, and GAD 9 revealed that,

“Naa gyud siyay transition, kay sauna ma remember nako sa attendance sheet every time naay activity specific yo female ug male lang to. Hantud gyud nga naa nay gender naay LGBTQ. Pero kadugayan naka adapt raman fud mam kay everything pwede raman siya ma learn. Like sa pag process ug liquidation naa siyay separate format nga GAD template.” (GAD 1)

[There was really a transition because, as I remember before, attendance sheets during activities only specified male and female categories. Eventually, gender categories included LGBTQ individuals as well. Over time, we were able to adapt because everything can be learned. For example, in processing liquidation, there is now a separate GAD template format.]

“ Katung first pa nga gina promote ang GAD maka ingon gyud ko nga ka hassle ba uie kay need pa namo utrohon amoang mga form kay need I integrate ang gender mga ing-ana, pero minimal raman hinoon. Karon, wala nman ky naka adapt nman, tapos thankful baya fud mi kay maka avail among program kay naa may budget ang GAD, 5% baya na siya” (GAD 2)

[When GAD was first promoted, I could really say that it felt troublesome because we had to revise our forms again to integrate gender-related aspects, although the changes were only minimal. Now, it is no longer difficult because we have already adapted. We are also thankful because our programs can benefit from GAD since it has a budget allocation of 5%.]

“sa paghandle nako as GAD Focal, cguro at first naglibog ko unsaon nako pagpasabot sa ilaha.. I mean sa mga Heads of offices kung unsay GAD ug unsaon pag mainstream si GAD, sa hinay.hinay na overcome raman fud na mga challenges, even until now..... naa raman gihapon ni na mga challenges samot nag kanang pa lahi. Lahi gud ang maghandle sa matag offices. Samot nag wala pa siyay basic knowledge about GAD so need pagyud e capacitate.” (GAD 9)

[In my experience as a GAD Focal Person, I was initially confused about how to explain GAD to the heads of offices and how to mainstream it. Gradually, those challenges were overcome, although even until now, the challenges still exist, especially because every office is different. It becomes more difficult when people do not yet have basic knowledge about GAD, so they still need to undergo capacity-building.]

“I always practice sensitivity and flexibility in my teaching approach. Even it makes difficult to consistently integrate GAD perspectives across different subjects but as an instructor I need to be resourceful. (GAD 3)

[I always practice sensitivity and flexibility in my teaching approach. Even though it is difficult to consistently integrate GAD perspectives across different subjects, as an instructor, I need to be resourceful.]

The findings suggest that GAD advocates view the implementation of gender-responsive practices as a continuous learning process that can be developed over time. Statements such as “ma learn raman noon siya” and “everything pwede raman siya ma learn” reflect a positive mindset toward adaptability and growth. This indicates that even if individuals initially lack knowledge or experience in GAD, they believe these competencies can be acquired through exposure and practice. Such perspectives highlight the importance of openness to learning and professional development in successfully implementing GAD initiatives. It also suggests that challenges in GAD implementation are not seen as permanent barriers but as opportunities for improvement and skill-building.

Moreover, the emphasis on sensitivity, flexibility, and resourcefulness in teaching demonstrates how educators actively adjust their approaches to become more gender-responsive. Practicing sensitivity allows teachers to better understand and respect diverse student needs, while flexibility enables them to modify strategies based on different classroom situations. Being resourceful also reflects the ability to maximize available materials and opportunities despite limitations. These qualities show that effective GAD implementation is not solely dependent on formal policies but also on the personal commitment and adaptive practices of educators. The findings highlight that teachers play a crucial role in translating GAD principles into meaningful and inclusive classroom experiences.

The findings of this study confirm that adaptive learning and flexibility are key coping mechanisms for GAD advocates in navigating challenges during the mainstreaming of Gender and Development (GAD) within higher education institutions. Participants described how they adjusted their approaches, learned gradually through experience, and remained flexible when institutional constraints, limited resources, or scheduling issues emerged. These adaptive behaviors reflect broader evidence in gender and mainstreaming

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research showing that responsiveness and flexibility enhance the effectiveness of gender initiatives in complex institutional settings. Kalbarczyk et al. (2025) mentioned that adaptive and reflective gender-responsive design frameworks have been proposed in other fields to ensure interventions remain inclusive and relevant to diverse user needs, highlighting the value of flexibility in addressing contextual barriers and tailoring strategies to changing conditions .

Similarly, research on gender-responsive practices in higher education emphasizes the need for flexible, inclusive pedagogical approaches that accommodate varying institutional climates and participant needs. Merma-Molina et al. (2025) noted that despite commitment among educators to integrate gender equality, systematic and adaptive strategies are required to meaningfully integrate gender perspectives into practice and respond effectively to implementation challenges. Casey and Wilson (2025) also mentioned that flexibility in teaching design and institutional practice supports inclusion and participation, allowing advocates to adjust methods and content to meet diverse stakeholder needs. These sources confirm that adaptive learning and flexibility are essential for coping with challenges and sustaining gender mainstreaming efforts in HEIs.

Collaborating and Building Support Systems. GAD advocates in higher education institutions utilize collaboration and support systems as a vital coping mechanism to address the challenges of mainstreaming gender and development. This strategy involves learning through experience and drawing on lessons from past initiatives to inform current practices. Inter-office collaboration and shared workload through teamwork enable advocates to distribute responsibilities effectively, enhance efficiency, and strengthen institutional engagement. Seeking expert support and participating in professional development opportunities, such as trainings and seminars, equip advocates with updated knowledge and practical skills to navigate complex GAD processes. Additionally, building external linkages and networks provides access to broader resources, guidance, and best practices, fostering collective problem-solving and sustainability. These collaborative and supportive approaches empower advocates to manage challenges effectively while advancing gender-responsive initiatives within their institutions. The main theme was backed up GAD1, GAD2, GAD4, GAD5, GAD 8 and GAD9, highlighting that,

“Makipag collaborate sa lain office aron ma realize ang program.”
(GAD 2)

[“We collaborate with other offices to help realize the program.”]

“Dili kaau dali ta ma stress kay dghan man committees din daghan mutabang sa mga lihokon aron ma realize ang program or activity kay tinabangay man.” (GAD 9)

[We do not get stressed easily because there are many committees and many people helping with the tasks to realize the program or activity since everyone works together.]

“Nagkuha gyud kog mga GAD experts as resource speaker.” (GAD 9)

[“I really invite GAD experts as resource speakers.”]

Linkages like sa mga other institutions like sa LGUS , we have also from NGOs nga naga advocate sila ana nga activities. (GAD 5)

[Linkages with other institutions such as LGUs are important. We also receive support from NGOs that advocate for these kinds of activities.]

“Sa akoa mam mas napadali siya or nagaan ang implementation sa program ug na meet ang mga goals na gina target through collaboration, support networks ug professional development. Pag ikaw raman gud isa mohilok lisud jud pero through support sa uban offices ug dili lang diria sa institution. Like pag naay training then mo tap sa Community Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (CDRRM) and other agencies mas napadali ang pag promote sa atung mga gender-responsive practices.” (GAD 1)

[For me, ma’am, the implementation of the program became easier and faster, and the targeted goals were achieved through collaboration, support networks, and professional development. If you work alone, it is really difficult, but through the support of other offices and not just within the institution, the work becomes easier. For example, whenever there are trainings, we tap the Community Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (CDRRM) office and other agencies, which helps us promote our gender-responsive practices more effectively.]

“we partner with the government here and naga invite mig mga experts here kay para maka conduct ug seminars. Katu last nag conduct sila ug psychological test. Kay para mahibal-an nila kung unsay ilang view on gender and developmetn programs.”(GAD 4)

[We partner with the government and invite experts so that we can conduct seminars. Recently, they conducted psychological tests to better understand participants’ perspectives on gender and development programs.]

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Sa pag route ug policies usahay naka affect siya sa akong work because it is time consuming. Kay daghan pman offices ang need e consider ang mag check, but, as always be patient lang gyud ko kay part man sa trabaho." (GAD 8)

[When routing policies, it sometimes affects my work because the process is time-consuming. Many offices still need to review and consider the policies, but I remain patient because it is part of the job.]

The findings show that overcoming challenges in Gender and Development (GAD) implementation is a gradual and ongoing process. Participants acknowledged that while progress has been made over time, challenges still exist, indicating that GAD work requires continuous effort and improvement. The idea of “as always be patient lang gyud ko kay part man sa trabaho” reflects resilience and persistence among GAD advocates, as they adapt to difficulties and patience rather than expect immediate solutions. This suggests that successful implementation is not linear but develops through experience, reflection, and sustained commitment. It also highlights that institutions need to remain flexible and responsive as they address emerging issues in GAD practice.

Furthermore, the findings emphasize that collaboration, capacity-building, and external support are key strategies in addressing these challenges. Working with other offices, forming committees, and engaging multiple stakeholders help distribute tasks and make implementation more manageable. Inviting GAD experts as resource speakers and participating in trainings and seminars enhance the knowledge and skills of implementers, leading to more effective programs. In addition, partnering with external agencies helps facilitate smoother and faster implementation of activities. These approaches show that addressing GAD challenges is a shared responsibility, where teamwork, continuous learning, and strategic partnerships play a vital role in strengthening implementation efforts.

The findings of this study confirm that collaboration and support systems serve as essential coping mechanisms for GAD advocates in addressing the challenges of mainstreaming gender and development (GAD) within higher education institutions. Hernandez et al. (2022) highlighted that engaging students and the community through participatory programs and outreach initiatives helps strengthen gender awareness, build shared responsibility, and enhance the social impact of GAD programs. Similarly, Gil (2021) emphasized that effective coordination among institutional units and networking with external organizations ensures coherent program implementation, prevents duplication of efforts, and provides technical and resource support. Mihrete (2021) also noted that collaboration with government agencies, non-governmental organizations, and other higher education institutions enhances the adoption of best practices and mobilization of resources, reinforcing the sustainability of gender mainstreaming initiatives.

Further supporting these findings, Rudnicka and Różalska (2025) argued that stakeholder engagement, including partnerships across institutional units and with external organizations, strengthens organizational capacity and fosters inclusive practices, enabling GAD advocates to navigate institutional resistance more effectively. Merma-Molina et al. (2025) highlighted that inter-unit coordination and community collaboration promote shared learning and provide structural support for program continuity. Raton-Hibanada et al. (2025) similarly emphasized that co-designing gender initiatives with external stakeholders enhances practical outcomes while reinforcing institutional commitment. These studies confirm that collaboration and support systems function not only as coping mechanisms but also as strategic tools that allow GAD advocates to implement gender mainstreaming more effectively in higher education contexts.

Managing Personal Coping and Emotional Regulation. GAD advocates in higher education institutions employ Personal Coping and Emotional Regulation as a key mechanism to manage the challenges of mainstreaming gender and development. This involves cultivating patience and perseverance to persist through institutional constraints and resistance, while maintaining a positive mindset that fosters resilience and motivation. Advocates practice emotional control and compartmentalization to prevent stress from affecting professional performance, alongside embracing acceptance and respect for differing perspectives within the academic community. Viewing feedback constructively further allows them to grow from experiences, refine strategies, and strengthen their advocacy efforts. These personal and emotional coping strategies enable advocates to remain focused, balanced, and effective in advancing gender-responsive practices within their institutions. This main theme was supported by GAD1, GAD2, GAD4, and GAD5. They shared that,

“Hinoon hawod manko mag compartmentalize, kung naay mga situation mga lisod, dili ra kaau ko makaingon nga affected ko. Kay all problems have solutions.” (GAD 4)

[Fortunately, I am good at compartmentalizing. When there are difficult situations, I cannot really say that I am deeply affected because I believe that all problems have solutions.]

“Since gina promote man gyud dria ang gender equality need to respect one another.” (GAD 2)

[Since gender equality is actively promoted here, there is a need to respect one another.]

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“Kaning dghan kaau kog learnings. For example I am more conscious on paano ko mo lihok, I am more conscious on how other people also act and treat other people”. (GAD 5)

[I have gained so many learnings. For example, I have become more conscious of how I act, and I am also more aware of how other people behave and treat others.]

“From doing counseling I also want a school sa better place for them. Kay kung nindot ang university nganong mag rant man sila , so, inga'ana gina take gyud nako as constructive criticism ang ilang mga rants related to GAD. I mean, ang specific lang gyud kung unsa ilang gina reklamo then kung dili gyud nila kaya muadtu ug OSA ako ang mag refer or relay kung ma ulaw gyud sila. Kay technically kung sa policy wala man gyud koy mabuhat. Maong gina refer lang gyud nako sila sa OSA. (GAD 4)

[Through counseling, I also want a better school environment for them. Because if the university is really good, why would they still be ranting? That's why I truly take their complaints related to GAD as constructive criticism. I mean, I focus specifically on what they are complaining about. Then, if they are not comfortable going to the OSA, I am the one who refers or relays their concerns if they are too shy. Technically, based on the policy, there is not much I can do, so I really just refer them to the OSA.]

“Base sa amoa, naga logbook man mi then gina isa.isa lang gyud ug ihap. Maong karon nga year amoa na siya usbon ang sa personnel ug sa students aron dali ra ma ihap then ma evaluation siya like pila gyud ka LGBTQ angna cater ug nahatagan sa services.”{GAD 1)

[Answer: Based on our practice, we record everything in a logbook and count them one by one. That is why this year we plan to change the system for both personnel and students so that it will be easier to count and evaluate, such as determining how many LGBTQ individuals were catered to and provided with services.]

The findings suggest that personal attitudes and emotional management play an important role in handling challenges in Gender and Development (GAD) implementation. Participants emphasized the value of patience, reflecting an understanding that change does not happen quickly and requires time and consistent effort. The belief that “all problems have solutions” shows a positive and solution-oriented mindset, which helps individuals remain motivated despite difficulties. In addition, the ability to compartmentalize emotions indicates a level of emotional control that allows GAD advocates to manage stress and continue performing their responsibilities effectively. These responses highlight that inner resilience and a constructive outlook are essential traits in sustaining GAD initiatives.

Moreover, the importance of respect and openness to feedback further strengthens effective collaboration and program implementation. Respecting one another promotes a supportive and inclusive working environment, which is essential in addressing gender-related concerns. Viewing criticisms or complaints as constructive rather than negative allows individuals to learn, improve, and refine their approaches. This openness helps reduce conflict and encourages continuous growth among GAD implementers. The findings show that beyond technical skills and policies, positive attitudes, mutual respect, and the ability to handle feedback are crucial in ensuring the success and sustainability of GAD efforts.

The findings of this study confirm that personal coping and emotional regulation are important mechanisms that enable GAD advocates to manage the emotional and psychological demands of mainstreaming gender and development (GAD) within higher education institutions. Advocates described how maintaining emotional stability, patience, and resilience helps them navigate resistance, limited support, and institutional stress, suggesting that managing one's emotional responses is central to sustaining their work. This aligns with the study of Dyar et al. (2024) showing that emotion regulation strategies can buffer the impact of stigma and stress, helping individuals manage negative affect and maintain psychological balance in challenging social contexts.

Moreover, evidence from broader educational and occupational settings underscores that effective emotion regulation and coping self-efficacy, the belief in one's ability to manage stressors, contribute to better adjustment and persistence in demanding roles. For example, Da Costa Dutra et al. (2023) found that adaptive regulation strategies such as social support, negotiation, and reappraisal are associated with positive adjustment and well-being among students and workers, suggesting that similar strategies may help GAD advocates regulate their emotional responses while implementing gender initiatives.

Ruiz-Camacho et al. (2025) also highlighted that active coping practices moderate stress responses, indicating that individuals who engage in constructive coping are better equipped to handle academic and organizational pressures. Taken together, these studies confirm that personal coping and emotional regulation are not merely psychological traits but key mechanisms that help GAD advocates sustain their efforts, adapt to setbacks, and remain engaged in the continuous work of gender mainstreaming.

Planning and Organizing GAD Implementation. GAD advocates in higher education institutions utilize Strategic Planning and Organizational approaches as a coping mechanism to address the complexities of mainstreaming gender and development. This involves the systematic use of documentation and monitoring tools to track progress, ensure accountability, and maintain organized records of initiatives. Advocates employ careful planning and contingency strategies to anticipate challenges and adapt to changing

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circumstances, while ensuring alignment with institutional policies and compliance requirements. Effective time and schedule management, along with strategies to manage workload constraints, allows advocates to balance multiple responsibilities and sustain the implementation of GAD programs. These planning and contingency strategies enable advocates to work efficiently, maintain focus, and achieve institutional objectives despite resource and operational challenges. This main theme was reinforced by GAD 1, GAD2, and GAD9. They shared that,

“Base sa amoa, naga logbook man mi then gina isa.isa lang gyud ug ihap. Maong karon nga year amoa na siya usbon ang sa personnel ug sa students aron dali ra ma ihap then ma evaluation siya like pila gyud ka LGBTQ angna cater ug nahatagan sa services.”{GAD 1}

[Based on our practice, we record everything in a logbook and count them one by one. That is why this year we plan to change the system for both personnel and students so that it will be easier to count and evaluate, such as determining how many LGBTQ individuals were catered to and provided with services.]

“Dili raman sa ingon nga naka affect siya, but the only thing I can do is to have more patience lang gyud cguro. Every plan activity dapat naay gyud Plan B if ever naay mga changes sa schedule dali raka maka adapt ug iwaa stress pa” (GAD 9)

[It did not really affect me in a negative way, but the only thing I can do is probably to have more patience. Every planned activity should always have a Plan B in case there are sudden changes in the schedule, so that you can easily adapt and avoid stress.]

“amoa gina follow ang mga memorandum order nga gina pagawas sa GAD office.” (GAD 2)

[We follow the memorandum orders issued by the GAD office.]

“ target planning with other offices aron ma plan out daan ang mga calendar of activities.” (GAD 9)

[Targeted planning with other offices should be done so that the calendar of activities can already be planned ahead.]

The findings indicate that careful planning, monitoring, and adherence to guidelines are important strategies in implementing Gender and Development (GAD) programs. The use of logbooks to track beneficiaries, such as members of the LGBTQ community, shows an effort to systematically monitor participation and evaluate program reach. This reflects a data-informed approach that helps institutions assess the effectiveness of their initiatives. The practice of preparing alternative plans (Plan B) also highlights the need for flexibility in managing activities, especially when unexpected challenges arise. In addition, following memorandum orders ensures that actions remain aligned with institutional policies and standards, promoting consistency and accountability in implementation.

Furthermore, the findings emphasize the value of coordination and forward planning in addressing challenges. Collaborating with other offices during the planning stage allows for better organization of tasks and clearer distribution of responsibilities. This proactive approach helps prevent potential issues and improves the overall flow of implementation. However, time and workload constraints remain a concern, particularly in integrating GAD into lesson planning. This suggests that while systems and strategies are in place, there is still a need to balance responsibilities and provide adequate support for educators. The findings show that effective GAD implementation requires a combination of structured planning, flexibility, collaboration, and time management.

The findings of this study confirm that strategic planning and organizational roles are important coping mechanisms that help Gender and Development (GAD) advocates navigate challenges in mainstreaming gender and development within higher education institutions (HEIs). Participants reported that providing advisory support for policy review and institutional decision-making enabled them to address gaps, align programs with mandates, and guide future directions, particularly in contexts where resistance, unclear policies, or implementation barriers occur. This aligned with Palma (2025), who noted that GAD advocates recommend policy revisions, evaluate program performance, and suggest innovative strategies to improve gender mainstreaming. Similarly, Tindowen et al. (2025) emphasized that the advisory role of GAD focal persons bridges gaps between policy formulation and practical implementation, ensuring consistency with institutional goals and improving organizational coherence.

Strategic planning also involves ensuring compliance with national mandates, which further strengthens institutional capacity and transparency. Gil (2021) reported that GAD advocates play a central role in aligning institutional initiatives with the *Magna Carta of Women*, CHED memoranda, and local GAD policies, promoting accountability and systematic compliance. Tindowen et al. (2025) also highlighted that GAD focal persons facilitate compliance audits and reporting, which maintain institutional accountability and monitoring frameworks. In addition to policy advisory functions, GAD advocates contribute to research and documentation of gender issues, as noted by Mihrete (2021), who observed that these activities help identify gender gaps, assess program effectiveness, and inform stakeholders.

Palma (2025) similarly emphasized that research supports evidence-based planning and enriches institutional knowledge for gender policy development. Hernandez et al. (2022) further highlighted that through needs assessments, priority identification, and strategic plan development, GAD advocates help guide institutional gender mainstreaming efforts. These studies confirm that strategic

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planning and organizational engagement serve as key mechanisms enabling advocates to navigate institutional challenges while ensuring sustainable implementation of GAD programs.

Promoting Advocacy through Training and Awareness. GAD advocates in higher education institutions employ Advocacy through Training and Awareness as a strategic coping mechanism to address the challenges of mainstreaming gender and development. This involves the conduct of seminars and symposiums that promote understanding and engagement among stakeholders, as well as continuous capacity building to enhance competencies in gender-responsive practices. Advocates also prioritize information dissemination to ensure that policies, programs, and initiatives are widely communicated and understood across the institution. Benchmarking best practices allows them to learn from successful models and adapt effective strategies within their own contexts. Through sustained awareness efforts and intentional perspective change, advocates are able to reduce resistance, foster inclusivity, and build a more supportive environment for GAD integration. These approaches strengthen both individual and institutional commitment to advancing gender responsiveness in the academe. This main theme was affirmed by GAD2, GAD5, and GAD9. They shared that,

“Provide all the information needed aron muattend sila. Since it is institutional activies man gyud either they like it or not dapat mo join jud sila. Sa mga students fud habang naga school sila dria they don’t have a choice kundi mo follow sa rules and policies.” (GAD 5)

[Provide all the information they need so they can attend. Since these are institutional activities, whether they like it or not, they are really required to participate. For the students as well, while they are studying here, they do not have a choice but to follow the rules and policies.]

“katung first nga naglibog ko kung unsaon sila pagpasabot sa GAD concept, akoa gibuhad is nag spearhead kog series of training's then nag kuha gyud kog mga GAD experts as resource speaker, and aside ana nag initiate kog benchmarking. Nag benchmark mi sa lain school nga kadtung naa na bitaw na GAD awards and naa nay mga best practices sa GAD.” (GAD 9)

[At first, I was confused about how to explain the GAD concept to them. What I did was spearhead a series of trainings, and I really invited GAD experts as resource speakers. Aside from that, I also initiated benchmarking activities. We benchmarked with other schools that already had GAD awards and established best practices in GAD.]

“Dako baya siyag tabang not only sa school but even my personal perspective like kanang naay mga GAD training na conduct makahatag baya siyag enlightenment kay una baya lahi baya gyud ang definition sa babae ug lalaki. Sa collaboration fud dako tabang in terms to budgeting siya.” (GAD 2)

[It is actually a big help, not only for the school but even for my personal perspective. For example, the GAD trainings that were conducted really provided enlightenment because before, my understanding of the definitions of women and men was very different. In terms of collaboration, it is also a big help, especially when it comes to budgeting.]

The findings show that continuous learning and awareness activities are key strategies in addressing challenges in Gender and Development (GAD) implementation. Conducting trainings and providing complete and clear information help address barriers by increasing understanding and encouraging participation. These efforts ensure that stakeholders are well-informed about the purpose and importance of GAD programs, which can reduce misconceptions and improve engagement. In addition, continuous capacity-building activities strengthen the knowledge and skills of implementers, making it easier to integrate GAD concepts into different areas of practice. This highlights that education and awareness are essential in creating a more supportive and informed institutional environment.

Moreover, the practice of benchmarking with other institutions reflects a proactive approach to improving GAD implementation. By learning from the experiences and best practices of other schools, institutions can adopt more effective strategies and avoid common challenges. GAD trainings also play a significant role in shaping perspectives, as they provide deeper insights and promote a more inclusive mindset among participants. These initiatives show that successful GAD implementation is supported by openness to learning, collaboration, and innovation. The findings suggest that strengthening knowledge, sharing practices, and continuously improving strategies are important in sustaining and enhancing GAD efforts.

The findings of this study confirm that advocacy through training and awareness functions as a key coping mechanism for GAD advocates in navigating the challenges of mainstreaming gender and development within higher education institutions. Participants highlighted their active roles in organizing seminars, workshops, and campus-wide campaigns to educate faculty, staff, and students about gender issues, promoting a shared understanding of equality and inclusivity. Mihrete (2021) emphasized that such initiatives raise awareness, foster engagement, and enhance institutional commitment to gender-responsive policies. Similarly, Palma (2025) noted that advocacy activities contribute to cultivating a culture of respect and inclusivity, reinforcing the importance of continuous institutional support in overcoming resistance and limited awareness.

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In addition to awareness-raising, GAD advocates facilitate capacity-building initiatives that strengthen the institutional ability to implement gender-responsive programs. Tindowen et al. (2025) reported that organizing gender sensitivity trainings and professional development programs equips university personnel with practical skills to apply gender perspectives across teaching, research, and administrative functions. Hernandez et al. (2022) further emphasized that such structured training empowers stakeholders, enabling them to address institutional gaps, integrate GAD principles effectively, and sustain long-term gender mainstreaming efforts. These findings confirm that advocacy through training and awareness not only enhances knowledge and engagement but also serves as a strategic mechanism for GAD advocates to manage institutional challenges, build capacity, and reinforce the sustainability of gender and development initiatives in higher education. Figure 3 present the

Figure 4. *Coping Mechanism of GAD Advocates on the Challenges in Mainstreaming Gender and Development within HEI*

Proposed Program Implementation Based on the Findings

The findings of this study reveal that GAD advocates develop meaningful learning from their experiences in mainstreaming Gender and Development within higher education institutions. These experiences are reflected in interconnected themes such as the development of gender awareness and advocacy mindset, the promotion of empathy, respect, and inclusivity, the strengthening of institutional policies and systems, the importance of capacity building and awareness programs, and the role of collaboration and

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support systems in sustaining initiatives. Through these experiences, GAD advocates enhance their commitment to gender responsiveness, improve their competencies through continuous learning, and contribute to fostering more inclusive academic environments.

However, despite these positive developments, the findings also indicate persistent challenges such as limited resources, varying levels of awareness, resistance to change, workload constraints, and gaps in coordination and institutional support. These challenges suggest that while GAD advocates demonstrate adaptability and resilience, their efforts remain constrained by structural and organizational limitations within higher education institutions.

In response to these findings, there is a need to develop a structured intervention that can address the identified gaps while strengthening existing practices. Thus, this study proposes the program titled “Enhancing Gender Equality Mainstreaming through Capacity Building and Institutional Support (EGEM-CBIS) Program Implementation Plan.” This proposed program aims to enhance the competencies of GAD advocates, strengthen institutional support mechanisms, improve collaboration among stakeholders, and promote sustainable gender-responsive practices. It seeks to bridge the gap between policy and practice and ensure a more effective, coordinated, and sustainable implementation of Gender and Development initiatives in higher education institutions. Below is the implementation plan of the proposed program “Enhancing Gender Equality Mainstreaming through Capacity Building and Institutional Support (EGEM-CBIS) Program Implementation Plan.”, as shown in figure 5.

Gender Issue/GAD Mandate	Supporting Statistics Data	GAD Objective	GAD Activity	Performance Indicator and Target	Target Date/Month of Implementation	GAD Budget	Lead or Responsible Office			
Limited awareness and understanding of Gender and Development (GAD), gender sensitivity, women's rights, anti-sexual harassment laws, and gender equality among personnel and students.	Based on office/community observations and attendance records, only 35% of personnel and students participated in previous GAD-related orientations. Majority of personnel/community members have limited knowledge regarding: Gender sensitivity, Safe Spaces Act, Anti-Violence Against Women and Children (VAWC), Magna Carta of Women, and Gender-responsive workplace/community practices.	To increase awareness and understanding of Gender and Development (GAD).	January: Orientation on Basic GAD Concepts and Gender Sensitivity	Number of orientations/seminars conducted	January-June	₱100,000	Gender and Development Office			
			February: Seminar on Safe Spaces Act and Anti-Sexual Harassment	6 activities conducted Participation rate At least 80% attendance						
		To promote gender sensitivity and equality in the workplace/community.	March: Women's Month Celebration and Advocacy Forum	Increase in awareness based on evaluation 85% of participants demonstrate improved awareness				-Training Expense	Student Affairs	
			April: Webinar on Mental Health and Gender Equality							-Materials and Printing
		To educate employees/community members on gender-related laws and policies.	To strengthen participation in GAD activities and programs.	May: Information on 18 th day Campaign to end VAWC				Distribution of IEC materials 100 brochures/posters distributed	-Snacks and Meals	Human Resource Office
				June: Midyear Monitoring and Evaluation				Submission of accomplished midyear accomplishment report and evaluation by all concerned offices	-Resource Speaker Honorarium	
						-IEC Materials (Tarpaulin, Posters, Flyers)				
						-Monitoring and Evaluation				

Figure 5. Enhancing Gender Equality Mainstreaming through Capacity Building and Institutional Support (EGEM-CBIS) Program Implementation Plan.

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The strength of the proposed program lies in its comprehensive and integrated approach to Gender and Development (GAD) mainstreaming within higher education institutions. Rather than treating GAD as a stand-alone or compliance-based requirement, the program operationalizes it as an institutional system that combines capacity building, stakeholder engagement, policy strengthening, collaboration, and continuous evaluation. This design is consistent with the findings of the study, which highlight both the enabling practices and persistent challenges experienced by GAD advocates in implementation.

Furthermore, the program is grounded on the principle that effective gender mainstreaming requires not only policy presence but also sustained institutional capability and coordinated action. The inclusion of continuous training and professional development directly addresses identified gaps in knowledge and skills among GAD advocates, thereby strengthening human resource capacity for gender-responsive implementation. This aligns with the view that capacity building is a critical determinant of successful GAD integration in educational institutions.

Moreover, the program intensifies implementation by expanding participation beyond GAD focal persons to include faculty, staff, and students. Through awareness campaigns, seminars, and institutional activities, GAD is embedded into the broader academic culture, reinforcing the principle of shared responsibility in achieving gender equality. This approach addresses the recurring issue of limited awareness and uneven participation documented in the findings.

The program also strengthens institutional sustainability by integrating GAD into planning and budgeting processes. This ensures that implementation is not dependent on ad hoc initiatives but is structurally supported through resource allocation and policy alignment. In doing so, it responds to documented constraints on funding and institutional support, thereby enhancing long-term viability.

In addition, the emphasis on collaboration and partnerships extends the institutional capacity of HEIs by leveraging external expertise and networks. This promotes knowledge exchange, benchmarking, and access to best practices, which are essential for improving program quality and innovation in GAD implementation.

The inclusion of monitoring, evaluation, and documentation mechanisms ensures that GAD initiatives are evidence-based and continuously improved. This strengthens accountability, supports data-informed decision-making, and contributes to institutional learning and policy refinement.

Effective Gender and Development (GAD) mainstreaming in higher education institutions (HEIs) requires an integrated approach combining policy support, capacity building, stakeholder engagement, and monitoring systems. A systematic review by Perez et al. (2025) highlights that successful GAD implementation is driven by robust policy frameworks, institutionalization of gender equality, stakeholder engagement, and strategic resource allocation, while persistent barriers include limited capacity, weak monitoring systems, and inadequate institutional support. These findings reinforce the need for structured programs that strengthen both human and organizational capacities in HEIs to bridge the gap between policy and practice.

Similarly, the OECD (2023) stressed that gender mainstreaming is most effective when embedded in institutional governance systems, budgeting processes, and sustained capacity-building mechanisms. The report emphasizes that without continuous training and institutional accountability structures, gender equality initiatives tend to remain fragmented and unsustainable. This supports the program's focus on training GAD advocates and integrating GAD into institutional planning and budgeting systems as a strategy for sustainability and effectiveness.

In addition, monitoring and evaluation are identified as critical components of successful gender mainstreaming. Wroblewski (2024) explains that effective gender equality policy implementation follows a cycle of planning, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation, where empirical evidence is used to improve program performance and accountability. This underscores the importance of establishing structured M&E systems within HEIs to ensure that GAD initiatives are continuously assessed and improved.

Furthermore, capacity building is consistently recognized as a key driver of effective implementation. The Philippine Commission on Women (PCW) emphasizes that GAD focal persons must undergo continuous training to effectively perform their roles in planning, budgeting, and monitoring gender programs, ensuring that gender perspectives are properly integrated into institutional operations. This aligns with studies showing that limited training and expertise significantly hinder GAD implementation in higher education settings (Perez et al., 2025; CHED, 2022).

Moreover, collaboration and stakeholder engagement are widely recognized as essential for strengthening GAD programs. Perez et al. (2025) and other studies on HEIs highlight that partnerships with government agencies, NGOs, and other academic institutions enhance access to resources, technical expertise, and best practices, thereby improving program sustainability and innovation in gender mainstreaming.

Effective GAD mainstreaming requires a comprehensive and coordinated system that integrates capacity building, institutional support, collaboration, and monitoring mechanisms. These findings provide strong empirical and theoretical justification for the EGEM-CBIS program, as it responds directly to identified gaps and aligns with global and national standards for gender-responsive governance in higher education.

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CHAPTER 4

SUMMARY OF THE FINDINGS, IMPLICATIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

In this chapter, the summary of the findings study is presented, from which implications and future directions are drawn.

Summary of the Findings

This section highlights the practical and forward-looking contributions of the study based on how GAD advocates mainstream gender and development within higher education institutions, how they cope with the challenges encountered in the process, and the insights gained in strengthening gender responsiveness in the academe. These findings are organized according to the research questions:

- 1) The findings on the lived experiences of GAD advocates in mainstreaming Gender and Development within HEIs revolve around the main themes of Institutionalizing GAD policies and practices, implementing GAD programs and strategies, collaborating and engaging with stakeholders, and experiencing challenges in GAD implementation.
- 2) The coping mechanisms of GAD advocates in addressing challenges in mainstreaming Gender and Development within HEIs are reflected in their use of adapting through learning and flexibility, collaborating and building support systems, managing personal coping and emotional regulation, planning and organizing gad implementation, and promoting advocacy through training and awareness.
- 3) The findings lead to the development of this program implementation titled “Enhancing Gender Equality Mainstreaming through Capacity Building and Institutional Support (EGEM-CBIS) Program Implementation Plan.” aiming to enhance the competencies of GAD advocates, strengthen institutional support mechanisms, improve collaboration among stakeholders, and promote sustainable gender-responsive practices.

The findings of this study affirm the principles of the Gender Mainstreaming Theory as articulated by the Council of Europe (1998, as cited in Kataeva et al., 2024). This theory emphasizes the integration of gender perspectives across all policy processes to ensure equality for both men and women, rather than treating gender issues as separate or secondary concerns. Consistent with this framework, the study revealed that GAD advocates actively embed gender considerations into institutional policies, programs, and practices within higher education institutions (HEIs). Participants highlighted efforts such as the institutionalization of GAD policies, mainstreaming gender in instruction, research, and extension, and establishing gender-responsive systems, practices that reflect the systematic reorganization and evaluation of institutional policies promoted by the theory.

Moreover, the study’s findings support the dual approach emphasized in the Gender Mainstreaming Theory, where gender equality is achieved both by addressing structural inequalities and complementing specific initiatives, such as awareness campaigns, training programs, and support services for diverse gender identities. GAD advocates demonstrated their role in influencing decision-making, fostering inclusivity, and ensuring that gender considerations are not merely symbolic but operationalized in everyday academic and administrative processes. This alignment between the findings and the theory underscores the importance of transforming institutional culture, promoting equitable opportunities for all genders, and sustaining long-term change in HEIs, thereby validating the relevance and applicability of the Gender Mainstreaming Theory in contemporary academic settings.

Implications

The findings of this study carry several practical and theoretical implications for advancing gender responsiveness within higher education institutions.

- 1) The emphasis on the institutionalization of GAD policies and practices underscores the need for universities to formalize gender-responsive frameworks through clear policy integration, compliance monitoring, and the establishment of sustainable systems. This suggests that institutional leaders must prioritize regular policy reviews, incorporate gender equity into organizational procedures, and allocate resources that ensure long-term continuity of GAD initiatives.
- 2) The implementation of GAD programs and strategies highlights the importance of equipping advocates with capacity-building opportunities, including trainings, seminars, and curriculum integration, while also encouraging resourcefulness and adaptability. Institutions should therefore provide structured professional development programs and allocate dedicated time for gender mainstreaming activities to enhance effectiveness and minimize fatigue or burnout among advocates.
- 3) The findings on collaboration and stakeholder engagement indicate that active coordination across offices, interdepartmental partnerships, and external linkages are vital to achieving shared ownership of gender initiatives. Institutional leaders and administrators should cultivate collaborative networks, establish mentorship and peer-support mechanisms, and promote participatory decision-making to strengthen engagement and ensure equitable distribution of responsibilities. The challenges identified, such as budget and resource constraints, scheduling conflicts, resistance to change, and limited awareness, highlight the need for strategic planning, advocacy campaigns, and proactive problem-solving to overcome barriers.
- 4) The study emphasizes the importance of adaptive coping mechanisms, including emotional regulation, personal resilience, and systematic planning, which can be nurtured through formal support systems, stress-management programs, and reflective practice.

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5) The findings suggest that strengthening Gender and Development (GAD) mainstreaming in higher education requires a well-structured and sustained program that develops both human and institutional capacities. The formulation of the “Enhancing Gender Equality Mainstreaming through Capacity Building and Institutional Support (EGEM-CBIS) Program Implementation Plan” highlights the importance of improving the competencies of GAD advocates through ongoing training and professional development. This ensures that they are adequately prepared and equipped to effectively design, implement, and sustain gender-responsive initiatives within their institutions.

Future Directions

Based on the findings, several future directions can be recommended to further strengthen gender responsiveness in higher education institutions.

School administrators

School administrators are encouraged to strengthen institutional support for Gender and Development (GAD) by allocating sufficient resources, establishing clear policies, and ensuring consistent monitoring and evaluation mechanisms. They should also promote a supportive environment that encourages collaboration among offices and recognizes the contributions of GAD advocates in mainstreaming gender-responsive practices within the institution.

GAD advocates

GAD advocates may continue to enhance their competencies through continuous capacity-building, training, and professional development activities. They are also encouraged to sustain adaptive practices, strengthen stakeholder engagement, and further promote gender awareness and advocacy initiatives to ensure the effective and sustained implementation of GAD programs.

Teachers

They are encouraged to integrate gender-responsive perspectives into their teaching practices and participate actively in GAD-related trainings, seminars, and institutional activities. They may also serve as role models in promoting inclusivity, respect, and equality within the classroom and the wider academic community.

Students

They are encouraged to actively participate in GAD-related programs, seminars, and advocacy activities to deepen their understanding of gender equality and inclusivity. They may also contribute to promoting a respectful and gender-sensitive campus culture by practicing awareness, challenging stereotypes, and supporting initiatives that uphold gender equality.

Higher Educational Institutions

They are advised to institutionalize comprehensive GAD frameworks that integrate policies, programs, and capacity-building initiatives across all levels of operation. They should strengthen inter-office collaboration, expand partnerships with external agencies, and sustain continuous evaluation and improvement of GAD implementation to ensure long-term gender mainstreaming and institutional transformation.

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APPENDIX A

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

I. Interview Proper

Preliminary Questions

1. How are you _____?
2. How do you feel that you are invited for this interview?
3. Do you think this would be a big help for you as a GAD Focal Person?

Research Questions	Interview Guide Questions	Probing Questions
What are the lived experiences of GAD Advocates in mainstreaming? gender and development within higher education institutions?	1. What specific strategies and programs do GAD Advocates implement to promote gender mainstreaming in higher education institutions?	1.2 What factors influence the effectiveness of these strategies and programs in achieving their intended gender mainstreaming goals within higher education institutions?
	2. How do GAD Advocates integrate gender-responsive policies and practices into academic and administrative systems?	2.1 What challenges do GAD Advocates encounter when integrating gender-responsive policies and practices, and how do they address these obstacles within the institution?
	3. In what ways do GAD Advocates engage faculty, staff, and students in advancing gender equality and inclusivity within the academic environment?	3.1 How do GAD Advocates ensure sustained participation and commitment from faculty, staff, and students in promoting gender equality and inclusivity initiatives?

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How do GAD Advocates cope with the challenges of mainstreaming gender and development within higher education institutions?	1. What specific challenges do GAD Advocates encounter in implementing gender and development initiatives within higher education institutions?	1.1 Can you describe particular situations where these challenges affected your work, and how you responded or adapted to overcome them?
	2. What coping mechanisms and adaptive strategies do GAD Advocates employ to address institutional, cultural, and logistical barriers to gender mainstreaming?	2.1 Can you provide an example of a specific strategy you implemented and explain how it influenced the integration of gender and development initiatives in your institution?
	3. How do collaboration, support networks, and professional development opportunities assist GAD Advocates in overcoming challenges in promoting gender-responsive practices?	3.1 In what ways do collaboration, support networks, and professional development initiatives enhance the capacity of GAD Advocates to effectively address obstacles and sustain gender-responsive efforts within higher education institutions?

Concluding Question

1. Are there more comments and ideas you would like to add before we end this session?

Closing Remarks:

The data gathered will be transcribed and a copy of the transcript will be sent to you for the confirmation of your answer. Once again, thank you very much for your participation in this In-Depth Interview. Your shared insights will be of great help for the success of this research endeavor. Thank you and have a nice day. May God bless you more!

 Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc.
RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE
RMC Buildings, Poblacion 8-A, Lopez Jaena
& F. Torres Streets, Marfori Heights, Davao City

ETHICS COMPLIANCE CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the study entitled "AGENTS OF INCLUSION: EXPERIENCES OF GENDER AND DEVELOPMENT ADVOCATES IN MAINSTREAMING GENDER RESPONSIVE PRACTICES IN THE ACADEME" prepared and submitted by: VANEZA C. PAQUIAO, a candidate for the degree of MASTER OF ARTS IN EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT, has been examined and evaluated by the RMC Research Ethics Committee (RMC-REC) to comply adequately with the requirements for research ethics protocol and is therefore cleared for implementation following the scientific procedures and internationally accepted guidelines.

Given this 17th day of December 2025 at the Rizal Memorial Colleges, Graduate School, Davao City, Philippines.

DR. RONALDO L. SERAS
RMC-REC Chairman

GS-RMC – Research Ethics Committee (REC FORM 2) | REVISION 2 | AUGUST 2024

**RIZAL MEMORIAL COLLEGES, INC.
GRADUATE SCHOOL**

RMC Buildings, 7-A, Lopez Jaena & F. Torres Sts.,
Marfori Heights, Davao City 8000

OFFICE OF THE DEAN GRADUATE SCHOOL

January 22, 2026

JENNIFER C. GONZAGA, DBM, LPT, CMITAP

Acting College Administrator
Samal Island City College
Datu Taganiog St., Samal District,
Island Garden City of Samal

Madam:

This is to respectfully endorse the request for permission of **MS. VANEZA C. PAQUIAO** a candidate for Master's degree to conduct a study entitled "**AGENTS OF INCLUSION: EXPERIENCES OF GENDER AND DEVELOPMENT ADVOCATES IN MAINSTREAMING GENDER RESPONSIVE PRACTICES IN THE ACADEME**" in partial fulfillment for the course leading to the degree of Master of Arts Educational Management (MA-EM).

Ms. Paquiao will coordinate with the acting college administrators to avoid disruption of classes endeavor.

Your support and concern for the educational growth of **Ms. Paquiao** is greatly appreciated.

Very truly yours,

NELIA BALAGTAS-AGA, PhD
Dean, Graduate School

Agents of Inclusion: Experiences of Gender and Development Advocates in Mainstreaming Gender Responsive Practices in the Academe

APPENDIX D

January 29, 2026

JENNIFER C. GONZAGA, DBM, LPT CMITAP
Acting College Administrator
Samal Island City College

Dear *Dr. Gonzaga*,

Mabuhay ug Madyawl

I am currently a Master of Arts in Educational Management (MAEM) student and am undertaking my thesis entitled "**Agents of Inclusion: Experiences of Gender and Development (GAD) Advocates in Mainstreaming Gender-Responsive Practices in the Academe**" as part of the academic requirements for the degree.

In this regard, I respectfully seek approval from your good office to conduct my study involving three (3) GAD Advocates, specifically an Instructor, the GAD Focal Person, and selected members of the GAD Focal Point System of your institution, through in-depth interviews. This study aims to generate meaningful data that will contribute to institutional development and support the implementation of evidence-based programs and interventions beneficial to the school community.

Rest assured that all information gathered will be treated with utmost confidentiality and will be used solely for academic purposes. Ethical research protocols will be strictly observed throughout the conduct of the study.

Attached herewith are an approved endorsement letter from my current school and a copy of my interview guide tool for your reference and consideration.

Should you have any questions or wish to inform me of the status or approval of this request, you may contact me at 0951-089-5250 or via email at paquiaovan03@gmail.com.

Hoping for your favorable consideration. Thank you very much for your kind support.

Respectfully yours,

VANEZA C. PAQUIAO, LPT
MAEM Student
Rizal Memorial College, Inc.

Approved by: 29 JAN 2026

JENNIFER C. GONZAGA, DBM, LPT CMITAP
Acting College Administrator
Samal Island City College

Agents of Inclusion: Experiences of Gender and Development Advocates in Mainstreaming Gender Responsive Practices in the Academe

January 30, 2026

JOY M. SORROSA, PHD
SUC President III
Davao del Norte State College

Dear *Dr. Sorrosa*,

Mabuhay ug Madyaw!

I am currently a Master of Arts in Educational Management (MAEM) student and am undertaking my thesis entitled "**Agents of Inclusion: Experiences of Gender and Development (GAD) Advocates in Mainstreaming Gender-Responsive Practices in the Academe**" as part of the academic requirements for the degree.

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VANEZA C. PAQUIAO, LPT
MAEM Student
Rizal Memorial College, Inc.

Approved by:

JOY M. SORROSA, PHD
SUC President III
Davao del Norte State College

February 03, 2026

MARLON D. MONTAÑO, DBM, CMITAP
School Director
UM-Peñaplata College

Dear *Dr. Montaño*,

Mabuhay ug Madyawl

I am currently a Master of Arts in Educational Management (MAEM) student and am undertaking my thesis entitled "**Agents of Inclusion: Experiences of Gender and Development (GAD) Advocates in Mainstreaming Gender-Responsive Practices in the Academe**" as part of the academic requirements for the degree.

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VANEZA C. PAQUIAO, LPT
MAEM Student
Rizal Memorial College, Inc.

Approved by:

MARLON D. MONTAÑO, DBM, CMITAP
School Director
UM-Peñaplata College

	<h2>SAMAL ISLAND CITY COLLEGE</h2> <p>Datu Taganiog Street, Brgy. Peñaplata, Samal District Island Garden City of Samal, Davao del Norte Email: samaliscitycollege@gmail.com Website: https://sicc.samalcity.gov.ph</p>	Form No.	
		Revision No.	01
		Date Effective	
CERTIFICATE OF APPEARANCE			
TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN:			
<p>This is to certify that the personnel, whose names appears below, appeared in <u>SAMAL ISLAND CITY COLLEGE</u> for the purpose as stated herein:</p>			
Name:	<u>VANEZA C. PAQUIAO</u>		
Designation:	<u>ADMINISTRATIVE OFFICER IV</u>		
Station:	<u>GAOU</u>		
Purpose:	<u>INTERVIEW - GRADUATE SCHOOL RESEARCH STUDY</u>		
<p>This certification is being in compliance with the standing regulation provided under Republic Act No. 3547 duly implemented by COA Circular No. 127 for the purpose of establishing the evidence and duration of his/her appearance hereto. The truth of which is hereby guaranteed by the certifying officer.</p>			
Place of Execution:	<u>SAMAL ISLAND CITY COLLEGE</u>		
Date of Execution:	<u>JANUARY 29, 2020</u>		
Certifying Officer:	<u>MERJE S. ABCEDE, RN</u> <small>Lic. No. 0707961</small>		

	<h2>HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT AND DEVELOPMENT</h2> <p>[] Main [X] Branch <u>Peñaplata</u></p>			
	CERTIFICATE OF APPEARANCE			
TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN:				
<p>This is to certify that Mr./Mrs./Ms. <u>Vaneza Paquiao</u> of <u>SICC</u> has appeared to the following office/s (Office/College/Branch)</p>				
OFFICE	DATE	PURPOSE	APPROVED BY HEAD OF OFFICE	SIGNATURE OF HEAD/ DESIGNATED OFFICER
<u>OSTC</u>	<u>Feb 11, 2020</u>	<u>interview</u>		<u>NICA L. MERJAS, RPN</u> LICENSE NUMBER <u>0030953</u>

F-16100-046/Rev. # 2/ Effectivity: October 8, 2018

**DAVAO DEL NORTE
STATE COLLEGE**

"Inspiring Change, Creating Futures"

president@dnsc.edu.ph ✉

dnsc.edu.ph 🌐

@officialdnsc 📺

New Visayas, Panabo City, 8105 📍

Office of the Director – Samal Campus

CERTIFICATE OF APPEARANCE

This is to certify that VANEZA C. PAQUIAO
has appeared in Davao del Norte State College – Island Garden City of Samal Campus on
30 JAN 2026

Given this 30 JAN 2026 at Davao del Norte State College
– Island Garden City of Samal Campus, Barangay Libuak, Island Garden City of Samal.

MARY GRACE O. RIMANDIMAN

Administrative Officer V

VISION

An institution leading in agri-fisheries and socio-cultural development in the ASEAN region

MISSION

DNsc shall produce future-ready workforce, create innovative solutions and technologies, empower communities, and uphold good governance towards sustainable development

CORE VALUES

Stewardship
Adaptability and Excellence
Integrity and Innovativeness
Love of God and Country

RIZAL MEMORIAL COLLEGES, INC.
 GRADUATE SCHOOL
 Lopez-Jaena & Torres Sts. Davao City
 Tel. No. 300-71-73

Validation Sheet for Qualitative Design

Name of Researcher: YANEZA C. PAQUIAO Degree Enrolled: _____
 Title of Research: AGENTS OF INCLUSION: EXPERIENCES OF GENDER AND DEVELOPMENT (GAD) ADVOCATES IN MAINSTREAMING GENDER RESPONSIVE PRACTICES IN THE ACADEME.
 Name of Evaluator: Sandra Lynn B. Binansac Dated: _____ Evaluated: _____
 Degree of Evaluator: PhD in Ed. Adm. Signature of Evaluator: [Signature]

- () 4 Very Good () 2 May be upgraded if revised
 () 3 Good () 1 For revalidation

To the Evaluator: Kindly check the column that fits your evaluation for the item.

Items	4	3	2	1
Ethics				
1. Introduction (purpose, confidentiality, duration and way of conduct and closing components (additional comments) are provided.	✓			
2. Informed consent is included.	✓			
Artistry				
3. Script included/built in, so interview can introduce, guide and conclude the interview in a consistent manner.		✓		
4. Questions are appropriate to the study enhancing the possibility of storytelling and narratives.	✓			
Rigor				
5. Questions are open-ended to encourage in depth responses; avoiding close-ended questions which are answered by "Yes" or "No".		✓		
6. Questions are stated in the affirmative manner.	✓			
7. Probing questions are provided.	✓			
8. Questions are logically ordered asking the highest priority first. Opinion questions follow information questions.	✓			
9. Questions are stated in clear and simple terms.	✓			
10. Number of questions can be covered within 60-90 minutes, not exceeding 15 open-ended items (probes excluded) for every research question, except special cases.		✓		

REMARKS: _____

ACSCU-ACI accredited: Master of Arts in Education Program

RIZAL MEMORIAL COLLEGES, INC.

GRADUATE SCHOOL

Lopez-Jaena & Torres Sts. Davao City

Tel. No. 300-71-73

Validation Sheet for Qualitative Design

Name of Researcher: VANEZA C. PAQUIAO Degree Enrolled: MAEM

Title of Research: EXPERIENCES OF GENDER AND DEVELOPMENT (GAD) ADVOCATES IN MAINSTREAMING GENDER RESPONSIVE PRACTICES IN THE ACADEME

Name of Evaluator: ERIC A. BORDIOS, PhD Dated: Evaluated: JAN. 15, 2026

Degree of Evaluator: PHD in DEVELOPMENT RESEARCH AND ADMINISTRATION Signature of Evaluator: [Signature]

() 4 Very Good

() 2 May be upgraded if revised

() 3 Good

() 1 For revalidation

To the Evaluator: Kindly check the column that fits your evaluation for the item.

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9. Questions are stated in clear and simple terms.	/			
10. Number of questions can be covered within 60-90 minutes, not exceeding 15 open-ended items (probes excluded) for every research question, except special cases.	/			

REMARKS: Interview Guide Questions are coherent with the Research Questions. They are also crafted in a succinct manner, making it more comprehensive on the part of the participants. It will surely yield good data.

ACSCU-ACI accredited: Master of Arts in Education Program

RIZAL MEMORIAL COLLEGES, INC.

GRADUATE SCHOOL
Lopez-Jaena & Torres Sts. Davao City
Tel. No. 300-71-73

Validation Sheet for Qualitative Design

Name of Researcher: VANERA C. PAQUIAD Degree Enrolled: _____
 Title of Research: AGENTS OF INCLUSION: EXPERIENCES OF GENDER AND DEVELOPMENT (GAD) ADVOCATES IN MAINSTREAMING GENDER RESPONSIVE PRACTICES IN THE ACADEME
 Name of Evaluator: PEY M. ANVARRO P.H.D Dated: Evaluated: _____
 Degree of Evaluator: Ph.D Signature of Evaluator:

- 4 Very Good 2 May be upgraded if revised
 3 Good 1 For revalidation

To the Evaluator: Kindly check the column that fits your evaluation for the item.

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9. Questions are stated in clear and simple terms.	✓			
10. Number of questions can be covered within 60-90 minutes, not exceeding 15 open-ended items (probes excluded) for every research question, except special cases.	✓			

REMARKS: _____

ACSCU-ACI accredited: Master of Arts in Education Program

Approved:

NELIA BALAGTAS-AGA, PhD
Dean, Graduate School

INTERVIEW GUIDE TOOL

Agents of Inclusion: Experiences of Gender and Development (GAD) Advocates in Mainstreaming Gender Responsive Practices in the Academe

I. Orientation of the Informant:

Good morning, Ma'am/Sir!

I, Vaneza C. Paquiao, a candidate for the Master of Arts in Educational Management of the Rizal Memorial Colleges, is currently conducting my thesis entitled **"Agents of Inclusion: Experiences of Gender and Development (GAD) Advocates in Mainstreaming Gender Responsive Practices in the Academe"**. In line with this, may I humbly request for your cooperation during the interview.

Before proceeding to the interview proper, I would like to make an emphasis that your participation in this study is voluntary and that withdrawal from participation in this interview is allowed. This activity will take only for 20 to 30 minutes. The entire conversation will be recorded so that the exact data which you are going to share will not be altered or changed and that the recall of the data will be exact. Please speak clearly in a loud and clear voice. The data or information gathered will be utilized purely for this research.

The purpose of this In-Depth Interview is to obtain your opinion on the results of my survey. I need your honest opinion in answering the following statements. Rest assured that your identity will be kept confidential and the data gathered will be interpreted in aggregate so as not to violate the ethical standards that have to be considered in the conduct of research.

Lastly, please feel free to clarify if there are statements which are not clear to you.

VANEZA C. PAQUIAO
Researcher

Informant/Participant

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Agents of Inclusion: Experiences of Gender and Development (GAD) Advocates in Mainstreaming Gender Responsive Practices in the Academe

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VANEZA C. PAQUIAO
Researcher

Informant/Participant

Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc.

RMC Buildings, Población 8-A, López Jaena
& F. Torres Streets, Marfori Heights, 8000 Davao City
(082) 300 71-73 Local 118

Graduate School

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

is hereby awarded to

Vaneza C. Paquiao

In grateful recognition of your outstanding contribution as a presenter at the **Graduate School Public Forum 2026** of Rizal Memorial Colleges, held on **May 3, 2026**. Your commitment to sharing knowledge and advancing research made the event better and inspired everyone who attended.

Theme: *"Advancing Graduate Scholarship: Elevating Standards,
Strengthening Impact"*

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Dante O. Calamba', is positioned above the printed name and title.

ATTY. DANTE O. CALAMBA, PhD
Officer-in-Charge, Graduate School
Rizal Memorial Colleges

APPENDIX H

PAQUIAO, VANEZA.doc

The Rizal Memorial Colleges

Document Details

Submission ID
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Submission Date
May 22, 2026, 4:37 PM GMT+8

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File Name
PAQUIAO, VANEZA.doc

File Size
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151 Pages
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176,365 Characters

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CURRICULUM VITAE

VANEZA C. PAQUIAO

Purok 4-A, Barangay Aundanao, Samal Dist.
Island Garden City of Samal
Paquiaovan03@gmail.com
09510895250

EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT

Post Graduate Studies : **RIZAL MEMORIAL COLLEGE**
Lopez Jaena Street, Davao City
Master of Arts in Educational Management
June 2026

Tertiary : **UM PENAPLATA COLLEGE**
Island Garden City of Samal
Bachelor in Elementary Education

Agents of Inclusion: Experiences of Gender and Development Advocates in Mainstreaming Gender Responsive Practices in the Academe

March 2018

Secondary : **SAMAL NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL**
Barangay Penaplata , Island Garden City of Samal
March 2012

Elementary : **PENAPLATA CENTRAL ELEMENTARY SCHOOL**
Barangay Penaplata , Island Garden City of Samal March 2008

Eligibility : **Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET)**

WORK EXPERIENCED

ADMINISTRATIVE OFFICERS IV

Samal Island Garden City of Samal
Datu Taganiog St., Barangay Penaplata, Island Garden City of Samal
July 2023 up to present

ADMINISTRATIVE OFFICERS II

Samal Island Garden City of Samal
Datu Taganiog St., Barangay Penaplata, Island Garden City of Samal February 2021 up to July 2023